

Soutpansberg Luvuvhu Landscape

Proposal to the Expanded Freshwater and Terrestrial Environmental
Observation Network (EFTEON)

University of Venda

Vuwani village, location of the University of Venda Vuwani Science Resource Centre, in 1951(left) and 2015.

Executive summary

The Soutpansberg, South Africa's northernmost mountain landscape, forms an island of mesic conditions supporting biodiversity within extremely heterogeneous habitats of strong physical, ecological, sociological, historical and contemporary land-use gradients from north to south and east to west, across multiple scales. Ecosystem services provided by these uplands, most important being water provision to large downstream human populations, depend on their preservation given rapid anthropogenically-induced change, largely resulting from pressing human developmental needs, within the context of potentially devastating global environmental change. The Soutpansberg and the Luvuvhu River catchment, the most important of the rivers originating in the mountains, form the landscape proposed for inclusion in the Expanded Freshwater and Terrestrial Environmental Observation Network (EFTEON).

The Soutpansberg Luvuvhu Landscape falls within a biosphere reserve, encompasses a strategic water source area, is culturally highly significant and contains the Thulamela municipality, one of only 14 local municipalities nationally with the highest priorities for ecosystem-based adaptation action based on its potential for adaptation, threats due to human development and biodiversity significance. The importance of the eastern part of the landscape is further reflected in the Greater Kruger Strategic Development Programme where all six cooperative zones of this strategy coincide.

Operational and logistical suitability of the landscape is underpinned by a wide body of local research and research expertise, complemented by national and international interdisciplinary research platforms aimed at reconciling resource conservation and development. Led by the University of Venda (specifically the South African Research Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change), an established national research infrastructure, the minimum requirements of long-term security of tenure and availability of facilities, data and opportunities to other researchers are met. There is synergy with existing research collaborations and great potential for development and continuation of these by building upon the EFTEON infrastructure. This is further strengthened by the University of Venda's focus on research and training (undergraduate and postgraduate) that are locale relevant and heavily informed by local stakeholder networks.

The core sites centred around the University of Venda, the Vuwani Science Resource Centre and the developing Thohoyandou National Botanical Garden are a platform for multi-decade operation and form a central node in the landscape at the epicentre of a rapidly transforming urban-rural gradient. Infrastructure at the university and established long-term international and national collaborations act as a springboard for broadened collaboration, driven by the University of Venda's aim to become a regional research leader. As a public institution, data will not only be open access, but the database platform provides for university-wide integration of current and envisaged socio-ecological studies at the institution. The existing eddy covariance flux tower at the Vuwani Science Resource Centre, established and maintained in collaboration with the Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture, Germany, is envisaged to be utilised for the EFTEON landscape and the basis of continuing multi- and bilateral programmes.

Proposed subsidiary sites include those at elevational extremes in the western Soutpansberg, characterised by sparse human population densities and the last remaining pristine ecosystems (including wetlands) in the landscape and long-term monitoring of iconic species. Further to the east, the Soutpansberg and Luvuvhu catchment stretch across a region with diverse and accelerating human developmental pathways. Subsidiary sites here include long term experimental work focused on ecosystem services on commercial agriculture farms (Levubu valley), long-term monitoring of river health in the strategic water source area and provincial (nature- and forest nature reserves) and state led (Kruger National Park) conservation initiatives further to the east in a rapidly expanding rural-urban matrix. The inclusion of monitoring sites in the more arid catchments of the Nzhelele River valley and a micrometeorological station array would allow for comparative studies along an aridity and anthropogenic impact gradient.

The regions' landscape heterogeneity is almost unequalled nationally, ranging from semi-desert to scarps that receive some of the highest rainfall in South Africa. This contrast will become more pronounced in future, with predicted equatorial climes in the east and desert conditions in the west over a distance of less than 70 km. There has been a long tradition of monitoring ecosystems in the landscape, supplemented with recent large-scale experimental studies testing various hypothesis related to ecosystem services and climate change. The elevational gradients and north-south contrast provide for templates where studies can be appropriately scaled, both in space, but also incorporating space for time substitutions. The university's long-term commitment to research and training also provides for the initiation and communication of compelling community engagement initiatives, not least through the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, itself a platform based on stakeholder involvement and which sets the stage for ground truthing of the effectiveness of zonation as well as the development of demonstration projects, two central objectives of this landscape conservation programme.

As with many areas of South Africa, water scarcity in the context of already constrained resources is a, if not the critical issue in the Soutpansberg region. The proposed landscape provides a natural laboratory of appropriate transitions and manageable size in which this issue, with such vital consequences for the whole country, can be monitored, researched in-depth and lessons learnt with interventions pioneered that could benefit other regions. The Soutpansberg Luvuvhu Landscape will benefit greatly from the deployment of EFTEON infrastructure informing local studies (and generating new questions) on coupled social and ecological, aquatic and terrestrial systems, inputting into land-use planning forums, determining the critical choice of sustainable or other local development pathways and adapting to and mitigating against global change.

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1. The proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape

The Soutpansberg (from Dutch, “salt pan mountains”), in the north-east of Limpopo Province and named for the endorheic basin at the north-west base, is the country’s northernmost mountain range. The proposed landscape incorporates the Soutpansberg Geomorphological Province (Partridge *et al.*, 2010) modified by Hahn (2011) and the upper catchment of the Luvuvhu River (Figure 1), the latter included to accommodate the continuity of this river, originating in and returning to the Soutpansberg. The total area is 7 761 km² of which the Soutpansberg *sensu stricto* is 6 696 km² and the upper-Luvuvhu 1 065 km². The proposed study area, the EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape (EFTEON-SLL), is selected as a cohesive physiographic feature to host the socio-ecological monitoring functions of EFTEON without necessarily excluding adjacent and downstream processes.

Figure 1. Proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape study area comprising the Soutpansberg Geomorphical Province and upper-Luvuvhu catchment indicating relief, drainage and places mentioned in the text.

The proposed core site of the EFTEON-SLL comprises the Vuwani Science Resource Centre (with existing eddy covariance flux tower and associated infrastructure), facilities at the University of Venda School of Mathematical and Natural Sciences (Thohoyandou) and the developing Thohoyandou National Botanical Garden. Proposed subsidiary monitoring sites are a platform for EFTEON that encompass the environmental

and land use gradients of the landscape with existing study sites in formal and informal conservation areas (Lajuma/Luvhondo, Medike and Nthakeni), provincial nature and forest reserves (Happy Rest, Nwanedi, Entabeni, Mphaphuli), potential other sites of significance in the landscape (e.g. Saltpan, Hanglip forest) (Figure 1) and existing facilities for hydrological and meteorological measurement (Figure 21).

Regional setting

The EFTEON-SLL is situated in the Vhembe District Municipality of the Limpopo Province which borders three Southern African Development Community (SADC) countries (Botswana, Zimbabwe and Mozambique) and with regional collaborative projects, including the Greater Limpopo and Mapungubwe Transfrontier Conservation Areas, the potential to have impact beyond South African borders (Figure 2). The Soutpansberg extends across and within four local municipalities (Thulamela, Makhado, Collins Chabane and Musina) with a young, growing population of ~1.4 million (Statistics South Africa, 2018) mainly residing in the southern and eastern parts of the mountain and foothills. The landscape is contained within the UNESCO Vhembe Biosphere Reserve (proclaimed 2009) with delineated core, buffer and transition zones.

Figure 2. The regional situation of the proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape indicating neighbouring countries, local municipalities, the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve area and transfrontier conservation areas.

During the Apartheid era the study area incorporated parts of the then-Transvaal Province and the Venda and Gazankulu “homelands” and a portion of the Kruger National Park. The political history and resulting socio-economic development pathways are critical to understanding contemporary patterns such as the concentrated distribution of population, land-use practices, levels of environmental degradation and other transitions resulting from very different drivers across the landscape. Figure 3 illustrates an overlay of land transformation (no natural remaining and ecological support area 2; Desmet *et. al.*, 2013) relative to these

past administrative areas. While 16% of the former Transvaal (excluding the Kruger National Park portion) within the EFTEON-SLL has seen land transformation, 26% and 34% of the former Venda and Gazankulu areas, respectively, have been wholly transformed largely through expansion of urban and peri-urban settlements (also see Figure 4).

Figure 3. The environmental impact of population growth and 87% - 13% land distribution? Contemporary land transformation shown within Apartheid era administrative areas in the proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape.

Geology and geomorphology

Trending east-west, the Soutpansberg extends approximately 210 km and from north to south it is 60 km at its widest and 15 km at its narrowest. It ranges in altitude from 200 m near Pafuri in the east, to Hanglip (Songozwi) 1 719 m (the second highest peak) and Lejuma 1 748 m (the highest peak) situated in the west (Hahn, 2011; Hahn, 2017). Geologically the Soutpansberg represents a volcanic-sedimentary succession, with underlying basalt formations overlain by quartzite (some of the earliest red beds) aged 1.6–1.8 Ga. (Hahn, 2011). Successive faulting ~150 Ma (Ranganai *et al.*, 2002) formed the Soutpansberg characterised by a succession of three predominantly east–north-east trending homoclinal ridges dipping between 15–35° to the north and rising abruptly in the south (Berthoud, 1903; Hahn, 2011). The most prominent feature of the Soutpansberg is the southern slopes forming high cliffs in the west, becoming a steep rolling landscape along the central section and with cliffs dominant once again in the eastern extremity.

Climate

The large tectonic transpositions of 20 Ma and 5 Ma contributed to the anomalous elevation of the eastern hinterland forming a characteristic escarpment, resulting in southern Africa's strong east-west climatic gradient (Partridge, 1998). With a warm wet season and cool dry season (May to September 12–22 °C and October to April 16–40°C, Kephe *et al.*, 2016) the Soutpansberg has highly contrasting seasonal climatic conditions with summer drenching and winter desiccation, particularly of the higher ridges dominated by lithosols (Mostert *et al.*, 2008). Entabeni, situated at the intersection of the Soutpansberg and the northern escarpment has an average annual rainfall of 1 874 mm, diminishing eastwards with Punda Maria receiving 545 mm. The rain shadow of the escarpment causes Louis Trichardt's rainfall to drop to 618 mm while the combined rain shadows of the escarpment and Soutpansberg cause Waterpoort to have the lowest recorded rainfall of 367 mm (Hahn, 2006).

A substantial proportion of the Soutpansberg precipitation results from regular cloud-immersion driven by moisture laden air from the Indian Ocean to the east interacting with the local orography and aerodynamics; much of the Soutpansberg biota is dependent on this phenomenon (e.g. Hahn, 2017). At Entabeni, fog precipitation has been measured at 1 366 mm per annum (Department of Environmental Affairs, 1988), thus considering Entabeni's average annual rainfall of 1 874 mm the average total meteorological precipitation could be as high as 3 240 mm per annum.

Hydrology

The main river systems of the EFTEON-SLL include the Luvuvhu, Mutale, Nzhelele, Nwanedzi and Sand (also known as the Muengedzi) within two water management areas, the Limpopo and the Luvuvhu-Letaba. Major discordant valleys are formed by the courses of the Sand, Mutale and Luvuvhu which cut across Soutpansberg stratigraphy, evidencing superimposition of drainage lines from the pre-existing Karoo landscape (Hahn, 2011). The Luvuvhu is the largest river originating from the Soutpansberg (referred to as the Pafuri on old maps; Jeppe, 1899) while the Sand is the only major river not originating from the mountains, rising 120 km to the south. All the rivers originating in, or flowing through the Soutpansberg, are tributaries of the Limpopo River (also known as the Vhembe River). Four large dams are located in the EFTEON-SLL, one on the Nzhelele, one on the Nwanedzi and two on the Luvuvhu, while one water body is South Africa's largest natural inland lake, Lake Fundudzi, located near the Mutale River headwaters. The latter is otherwise free-flowing and a flagship, being wholly included as a Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Area (FEPA; ecological categories A, AB or B), as is the Sand River downstream of the Soutpansberg and portions of the Luvuvhu (lower catchment) and Nzhelele and Nwanedzi rivers (upper catchments/tributaries). However, the majority of the latter three rivers are classed as moderately to heavily modified (Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, 2011).

Land-use

Main contemporary land-use of the EFTEON-SLL comprises silviculture, commercial and subsistence agriculture, pastoralism, conservation, game farming and human settlements. Land cover is 71% natural

woodlands and forests, 5% grasslands, 13% silviculture, orchards and active and fallow agricultural land and 10% human settlements and infrastructure (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2018; Figure 4).

Figure 4. Proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape illustrating 2018 National Land Cover (reclassified).

Commercial silvi- and agriculture dominate the central-southern sections of the landscape especially in the upper catchment (high rainfall areas) of the Luvuvhu River. North and east of this the land-use transitions rapidly into densely populated regions (traditional authority areas corresponding to the ex-"homelands") characterised by extensive rural and urban settlements and subsistence agriculture, becoming more lightly populated towards the Kruger National Park. The western and northern parts of the study area are more arid with a strong focus on conservation and game farming in the sparsely inhabited western Soutpansberg where montane landscapes have largely seen abandonment of agriculture over the last century, although the northern and southern bases of the western part of the mountain are characterised by extensive pivot agriculture.

2. Suitability of the landscape

2.1. General situational characteristics of the landscape

The EFTEON-SLL is a landscape of particular biological significance and strategic regional location (“a key opportunity”; Limpopo Province, 2016) with the potential to observe global change processes over strong climatic, ecological (including biological invasion), sociological, historical and contemporary land-use gradients from north to south and east to west across multiple scales. Thulamela, home of the University of Venda and Vuwani Science Resource Centre, is one of 14 local municipalities identified nationally as a priority for ecosystem-based adaptation given threats to its biodiversity from human development and importance of its ecological infrastructure (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2019).

2.1.1. Strategic Water Source Areas

The EFTEON-SLL incorporates the majority of the Soutpansberg Strategic Water Source Area (SWSA; both surface- and groundwater resources) and the far west of the study area incorporates a portion of the Vivo-Dendron groundwater SWSA (Water Research Commission, 2017; Le Maitre *et al.*, 2018; Figure 5).

The Soutpansberg SWSA (surface water area 2 345 km² with mean annual runoff of 2 267 m³/ha; Le Maitre *et al.*, 2018), which falls largely within highly populated and intensive agri- and silvicultural areas, provides baseflows of >200 mm/annum and recharge rates of >65 mm/annum within a region of very low base flows of <1 mm/annum. Despite this, little of the SWSA is under formal protection (surface water protected area is 2.6% and groundwater protected area is 2.8%; le Maitre *et al.*, 2018) and it is characterised by extensive urban areas and dense rural settlements while the Luvuvhu River system originating within it is under stress from over-allocation and current and future intra- and inter-basin transfer schemes (Le Maitre *et al.*, 2018). Commercial agriculture and human settlements surrounding the western Soutpansberg in particular, are heavily dependent on groundwater reserves (Van Niekerk *et al.*, 2018; and to an extent direct abstraction from Soutpansberg streams at the northern base) as evidenced through the predominance of pivot-irrigation in this more arid western part of the study area.

Improved understanding of the climate, geomorphology and resultant hydrological processes that lead to runoff generation, baseflow and groundwater recharge/discharge is critical to the preservation of the mountain’s perennial streams, rivers and aquifers, linking to sustainable development planning, water sensitive design and (downstream) human benefits in line with Water Research Commission recommendations (Le Maitre *et al.*, 2018). Equally, quantification of the use of groundwater for agriculture is critical to protection of this resource with Limpopo having the highest percentage use of irrigation for crops nationally (Van Niekerk *et al.*, 2018) although the Luvuvhu-Letaba area uses most ground water for human consumption, a trend likely to increase with surface water over-utilised (e.g. Allwright *et al.*, 2013). Natural and non-natural land cover transitioning across local catchments and historic and future local and global change impacting these offer an ideal opportunity to investigate processes and threats to SWSAs in the

coupled aquatic and terrestrial systems across a hierarchy of differently affected (anthropogenically; for example, across silvicultural, communal and conservation areas) stream orders.

Figure 5. Proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape comprising the Soutpansberg Geomorphic Province and upper-Luvuvhu catchment indicating Strategic Water Source Areas, stressed quaternary catchments and sub-Water Management Areas.

Noting the largely orographic rainfall of the Soutpansberg and the largely unquantified (although see Department of Environmental Affairs, 1988) though critical (for reliant ecological communities and water provision, supplementing precipitation and decreasing evapotranspiration) contribution of frequent cloud immersion (resulting from advection and condensation of moist maritime air; with reasonable prospects for development of fog water harvesting systems; Olivier and van Heerden, 2003), direct recording of fog precipitation (and coupled ceilometer and remote sensing measurement of hydrometeors e.g. optical thickness and cloud base heights) would allow for incorporation of these phenomena into hydrological models and detection of threats from global warming (e.g. higher cloud bases throughout seasons; Van Beusekom *et al.*, 2017).

The EFTEON-SLL also provides the opportunity for refined modelling and delineation of the SWSAs with improved interpolation of rainfall surfaces (as recommended by Le Maitre *et al.*, 2018 and given data deterioration through declining numbers of weather stations; e.g. Bailey and Pitman, 2015; Foden *et al.*, 2019) or river flows (for example the perennial Kutetsha and Sandsloot streams of the far-western Soutpansberg are un-surveyed) from extended meteorological/flow observation at subsidiary sites.

2.1.2. Biodiversity hotspots, pattern and process

The EFTEON-SLL features a diverse interchange of habitats which can range from Afro-montane forest to mesic montane grassland to semi-arid vegetation within a few kilometres, forming a continuous mosaic resulting from extremes of geomorphological complexity (altitude, aspect and slope) and a multitude of succeeding micro-climates on the smaller scale (Hahn, 2017). High diversity patterns across flora and fauna can be attributed to geographical location and resultant ecological processes from a meeting of physiographic influences (Afro-montane, Kalahari, Maputaland, lowveld and tropical; e.g. Hahn, 2006; Kirchof *et al.*, 2010) on the broader scale. A large number of endemic species occur, and relict populations are of phylogenetic importance. For example, the Soutpansberg harbours near-endemic mountain-relict species or subspecies of horseshoe bats (Taylor *et al.*, 2012), forest shrews (Taylor *et al.*, 2013c), samango monkeys (*Cercopithecus albogularis schwarzi*; Dalton *et al.*, 2015) and reptiles as described below.

Figure 6. Soutpansberg plant endemics. Clockwise from top left: *Mystacidium braybonae*, *Kalanchoe crundallii*, *Huernia whitesloanea*, *Aloe hahni*, *Delosperma zoutpansbergense*, *Zoutpansbergia caerulea* and *Aloe angelica*. Photographs: I. Gaigher & B. Linden.

The Soutpansberg is a Centre of Plant Endemism (Van Wyk and Smith, 2001; Hahn, 2017) with 22 narrow endemics (although this rises to 44 taxa if including the (eastern) adjacent Blouberg inselberg and Makgabeng cuesta). Of the endemic species 61% occur within the mistbelt region and 41% are restricted to it with 10 of these being succulents. In times of drought a large percentage of the high-altitude mountain flora survives on precipitation resulting from the regular mist. Asphodelaceae is the most species rich family of Soutpansberg endemic taxa, with six species in the genus *Aloe*. Both Apocynaceae and Asteraceae contain four genera with five taxa. The Soutpansberg is also noted as a centre of floristic diversity with 2 443 vascular plant taxa (within 922 genera and 187 families) constituting 74% of vascular plant families of southern Africa and 49% of southern African genera within the ~6 700 km² area. This higher order diversity, the greatest

among South African centres of endemism (and mirrored by the regional endemic flora with 44 taxa within 32 genera and 32 families) is indicative of the importance of the mountains as a biological refugium (Hahn, 2017; Hahn, 2019).

Phytogeographic patterns are mirrored by faunal diversity and endemism albeit with most sampling occurring in the conservation areas of the western Soutpansberg or the Kruger National Park in the east. Recording in Luvhondo Nature Reserve (~4 300 ha) has yielded 84 mammal taxa (Lajuma Research Centre, in prep.) to which six annual camera trap surveys over ~200 km² of the western Soutpansberg by Panthera (monitoring the leopard population) have added a further 21 mammal species (South African leopard monitoring project, Lajuma camera-trap survey 2014–2019). Of particular relevance is the role of the mountain as refugium for leopard (*Panthera pardus*) populations, grassland species such as mountain reedbuck (*Redunca fulvorufula*), forest species such as red duiker (*Cephalophus natalensis*) and samango monkey. It is one of the few landscapes where all five South African primate species occur sympatrically, with long-term research (5–15 years) across all these taxa at Lajuma Research Centre. The Soutpansberg is highly diverse in bats (Taylor *et al.*, 2013a, Taylor *et al.*, 2013b; Taylor *et al.*, 2015b, Weier *et al.*, 2017) and terrestrial small mammals, including rare species (Taylor *et al.*, 2013c). Vulnerable and fragmented high-elevation Soutpansberg Sourveld Summit grassland small mammal communities are particularly threatened by climate change (Taylor *et al.*, 2016, Taylor *et al.*, 2017).

The western Soutpansberg is a hotspot of lizard diversity and endemism with emphasis on species of conservation concern (Bates *et al.*, 2014) and a hotspot of increasing erosion of reptilian phylogenetic richness (Tolley *et al.*, 2019). Long-term surveys in the far west of the mountain have recorded 96 taxa in 67 genera and 16 families including 11 endemic or near-endemic to the Soutpansberg (Kirchhof *et al.*, 2010; van Huyssteen and Petford, Biodiversity Lists of the western Soutpansberg, unpublished data). The reptile community clearly shows effects of isolation with the mountain historically acting as a topographic climate buffer and island of mesic conditions during aridification events, resulting in the presence of mesic-adapted endemic and relict species (Kirchhof *et al.*, 2010a). Petford *et al.*, (2019) modelled habitat preferences of (largely montane) endemic, rupicolous reptile taxa and found that most species were limited by climatic factors with implications for their conservation under global change.

Most of the Soutpansberg falls within the Birdlife International Soutpansberg Important Bird Area (IBA) triggered by, amongst other important species, the presence of a breeding population of between 116–171 Endangered Cape vultures (*Gyps coprotheres*). The latest monitoring assessment (2014) considers the Soutpansberg IBA to be in a very unfavourable condition and under very high threat due to agricultural expansion and intensification of biological resource use (BirdLife International, 2020).

A third of all known spider species in South Africa are found in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve area (717 species) of which 80% are found on the Soutpansberg (including 297 species in 49 families in an area of ~450 ha) five of them endemic to the mountains and four listed as Vulnerable based on the national Red List (e.g. Foord *et al.*, 2002; Foord *et al.*, 2008). All the rare and endangered spider species of the region are found on the Soutpansberg mountain (Foord *et al.*, in press). Scorpion diversity is high and the western Soutpansberg is considered a hotspot with 19 species in eight genera and three families collected in an area

of 16 km² (Foord *et al.*, 2015) and 22 species recorded for the area by van Huyssteen and Petford (Biodiversity Lists of the western Soutpansberg, unpublished data).

There are a number of endemic beetles in the Soutpansberg. *Pentatrachyphloeus lajumensis*, *P. rudyardi*, *P. schoemani* and *P. soutpansbergensis* are all highly localized entomine weevils found in very specific sites (Borovec and Skuhrovec, 2019). *Anaxius bloubergensis* is an endemic darkling beetle from the Blouberg (Kamiński and Schoeman, 2018a). The endemic genus *Zoutpansbergia* is comprised of two darkling beetle species *Z. serricostata* and *Z. schoemani* that occur only in the western reaches of the range (Kamiński and Schawaller, 2018). *Bantodemus lajumaensis* is also highly restricted to the western range (Kamiński and Schoeman, 2018b). The endemic ground beetle *Wahlbergiana alternans* is found only in the Afromontane forests of the mountain, while endemic dung beetles include *Scarabaeus schultzeae*. Most of these endemics have only been described within the last three years.

2.1.3. Conservation initiatives

The EFTEON-SLL incorporates a portion of the northern Kruger National Park, several provincial and private or traditional authority nature reserves and forest nature reserves and one protected landscape (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2020). The Greater Kruger Strategic Development Programme identifies a substantial portion of the eastern EFTEON-SLL as falling within the Kruger National Park land use and expansion area (having significant conservation and biodiversity economy development potential), socio-economic priority area and water priority and institutional integration areas (Greater Kruger Strategic Development Programme, 2020). Priority programmes in the Mutale-Soutpansberg corridor include climate change mitigation and adaptation, restoration of ecological infrastructure, SWSA monitoring and management (including transboundary catchment management), biodiversity stewardship, sustainable resource use, innovative financing for these priorities and integration into land use planning.

The biodiversity of the Soutpansberg was one of the main motivations for the 2009 proclamation of the UNESCO Vhembe Biosphere Reserve (VBR) (Dombo *et al.*, 2006). Substantial work has been facilitated by the VBR over the last decade, particularly in terms of biodiversity assessment and conservation planning (including broad stakeholder engagement) with input to, and alignment with, regional plans (e.g. Desmet *et al.*, 2013; Desmet and Cloete, 2014; Vhembe District Municipality, 2017) emphasising that the current protected area network is not representative of biodiversity pattern and lacks connectivity for maintenance of ecosystem functioning and genetic diversity. To this end the VBR has begun the work of identifying future, more representative zonation (Strategic Environmental Focus, 2016).

The far western Soutpansberg was included in the 2009 National Protected Area Expansion Strategy (Government of South Africa, 2010) under the Blouberg-Langjan focus area while the updated priority focus areas include natural land across both the east and west of the mountain (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2016). The Limpopo Conservation Plan (Desmet *et al.*, 2013) categorises 52% of the EFTEON-SLL as Critical Biodiversity Areas (irreplaceable). Birdlife South Africa includes the Soutpansberg as an Important Bird Area (BirdLife International, 2020). Private initiatives have seen the proclamation of conservation areas in both the east and west including Luvhondo Nature Reserve (designated 2014) and Mphaphuli Protected

Environment (designated 2018) (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2020). The Endangered Wildlife Trust (EWT) supported by the Limpopo Department of Economic Development; Environment and Tourism (LEDET) is leading a project, the Soutpansberg Biodiversity Stewardship Initiative, within the Limpopo Biodiversity Stewardship Programme to have a further 27 000 ha within 37 cadastres (farms and farm portions of which 98% are within Critical Biodiversity Area 1 and with landowner agreement secured) brought under conservation, the majority in the western Soutpansberg, towards an overall project: the Soutpansberg Protected Area.

Figure 7. Proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape indicating Limpopo Conservation Plan categories (2013) and 2020 Protected Areas. Note that there is a discrepancy between Protected Areas included in the Limpopo Conservation Plan and the Protected Areas database due to certain Apartheid-era reserves not having been gazetted.

2.1.4. Areas of high carbon sequestration potential

South Africa has a mean total environmental organic carbon (TEOC) of 6 396 gC.m⁻², mean gross primary production (GPP) of 373 gC.m⁻² and mean net primary production (NPP) of 186 gC.m⁻² (South African Carbon Sinks Atlas, 2017). In comparison the EFTEON-SLL, largely situated within the high rainfall areas of South Africa and indicative of the potential for carbon sequestration (yet with widely ranging values corresponding to the highly heterogenous landscape), has a mean TEOC of 10 610 gC.m⁻² (range 662–50 339; Figure 9), a mean GPP of 772 gC.m⁻² (range 116–815) and a mean of NPP 386 gC.m⁻² (range 58–908) (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2015b).

Differing land use practices and the role of drivers (and loss or gain of these) such as fire and herbivory over the broad east-west transition of the EFTEON-SLL have seen resultantly different changes with

consequences for carbon storage and fluxes including future sequestration potential. While the eastern areas have seen substantial deforestation linked to population pressure (e.g. Munyati and Kabanda, 2009) and agriculture, the southern slopes of the central and western parts have seen rapid (~100 years) succession from grassland to woodland/thicket through bush encroachment/invasion (Hahn, 2018; Figure 8, also note the high TEOC of the southern slopes of the drier western Soutpansberg in Figure 9), in line with national

Figure 8. Looking west across the southern slopes of the Soutpansberg with Hanglip in the background. Left: Photograph taken before 1920 (Giesekke Private collection). Right: Photograph taken in November 1999. C Hanglip. (Hahn 2017).

Figure 9. Proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape illustrating total environmental organic carbon (TEOC) in $gC.m^{-2}$.

trends (Foden *et al.*, 2019), with potential for quantification (long term monitoring plots) and understanding of carbon cycle feedbacks over the landscape, improving understanding of carbon stocks and fluxes and applying these for mitigation interventions (e.g. re- or afforestation of peri-urban areas, low tillage agriculture, managed fire regimes) specific to processes in the study landscape (National Terrestrial Carbon Sink Assessment, 2015; Foden *et al.*, 2019).

The more open landscapes in the less populated traditional authority areas of the east are juxtaposed against rapid woody encroachment in the central and western parts of the EFTEON-SLL and are unexplained. The derivation of historical (current) land use practices, such as fire frequency and vegetation change, from remotely sensed burned area products (e.g. Roy *et al.*, 2019) such as the 20-year burned area time series for South Africa being developed by the Centre for Scientific and Industrial Research, would possibly assist to explain the persistence of more open landscapes in the east. Further potential exists for quantifying CO₂ sequestration within the extensive silvicultural operations (~4% of the study area; through plantation inventory and management records while integrating site factors such as climate, topography and soils; e.g. Dovey, 2014) in the central and east of the Soutpansberg, particularly amongst the large corporate operations.

2.1.5. Landscapes of high cultural value

The Palaeolithic in the wider Soutpansberg area is reflected in artefacts found dating from the Oldowan-Acheulean (from ~2 Ma) through the Middle- (from ~250 ka) to Late Stone Age (from ~45 ka) (the date of emergence of any one culture being an outcome of complex and nonlinear evolutionary trajectories over regions; d'Errico *et al.*, 2017). The Late Stone Age is especially well-represented in the area with numerous rock art sites characterised by deposits of microlithic stone-tools (Eastwood and Eastwood, 2006). Early-Middle- and Late Iron Age sites (some with similar developmental chronologies of those of the Mapungubwe World Heritage Site ~80 km to the north) including those detailing the development of the Vhavenda nation (and to the south the Gaza Kingdom under Soshangane) are present. The earliest known Iron Age archaeological sites within the Soutpansberg are Happy Rest (350–470 AD) and Klein Africa (450–660 AD), cultures that also herded goats, sheep and cattle (Voigt and Plug, 1984) although Iron Age people were known to be present before this and probably associated with an observed increase in fire and decrease in tree pollen from ~1 500 BP onwards (Scott, 1987). More recent sites are distributed across the Soutpansberg including Thulamela, a 13th-17th Century stone walled, hilltop site in the Kruger National Park emblematic of the south-eastern limits of the Zimbabwe culture (Steyn *et al.*, 1998) and Dzata characteristic of the unique development, under Singo rulers, of the Vhavenda nation from Shona and Ngoni antecedents (e.g. Ralushai, 1977; Loubser, 1991).

People of European descent arrived in the area from the 1820s onwards, trading in wildlife products (ivory, horns, skins and meat) and timber from the Soutpansberg forests including Sneezewood (*Ptaeroxylon obliquum*) and Outeniqua yellowwood (*Afrocarpus falcatus*). Notable early characters who settled in the area and took local wives included João Albasini and Coenraad de Buys, the descendants of the latter still resident in Buysdorp in the western Soutpansberg. In 1848 the first settler village of Zoutpansbergdorp, later renamed Schoemansdal (a cultural museum today), was established and lasted until 1867 when the Vhavenda King

Makhado forced its evacuation. The Vhavenda were the last South African people to be subjugated, at the end of the 1890s, under the northward expansion of European influence. The first European church missions (most prominent was the Berlin Mission with seven stations) were established in the area during the second half of the 19th Century (Tempelhoff, 1999; Dombo *et al.*, 2006; Hahn, 2018). The area has a notable and notorious Anglo-Boer War (or South African War) history with many of the war crimes committed locally by the Bushveldt Carbineers still a matter of international disagreement (Leach, 2012).

Today the main cultural groups of the EFTEON-SLL include the Vhavenda (the majority), Tsonga/Shangaan, Northern Sotho, the Buys community and South Africans of European and Asian descent. There is a strong contemporary developmental focus on the cultural heritage of the area (e.g. Vhembe District Municipality, undated), specifically traditions such as wood carving, revival of traditional horticulture and ethno-botany and the potential for sacred sites (such as Lake Fundudzi) as tourist attractions, although the latter being not without contention (e.g. Ratiba, 2013).

2.1.6. Areas of anticipated significant land use- or social change

Land use change and social change are linked to expected development pathways for the region (section 3.4). According to the Vhembe District Bioregional Plan, agricultural expansion, growth of human settlements and mining projects are the principal pressures on biodiversity with human settlements and associated land uses encroaching on Critical Biodiversity Areas and Ecological Support Areas (Vhembe District Municipality, 2017). Agricultural and urban expansion (with corresponding deforestation) are particularly rapid in the high rainfall Luvuvhu and Nzhelele catchments which have seen very substantial land cover change from forest, woodland and grassland to commercial and subsistence agriculture and human settlement as well as degraded areas (e.g. Kundu *et al.*, 2015), these same drivers of change identified in community livelihood surveys in the two catchments (Walter *et al.*, 2020). Increased water abstraction across the region (as observed, e.g. Van Niekerk *et al.*, 2018), from both ground and surface sources, is likely given the predominance of urban, agricultural and mining development.

Spatial and resource inequalities (a disjuncture between centres of population and centres of socio-economic opportunity; Department of Rural Development and Land Reform, 2016) combined with population growth have led to widespread environmental degradation particularly in the ex-'Homelands' which can be expected to continue. High, direct reliance on natural resources (and concomitant direct land degradation/deforestation, e.g. Munyati and Kabanda, 2009) by the population of the district is exemplified by the fact that 63% of households still rely on firewood for cooking (Rasimphi and Tinarwo, 2020). Further changes to land tenure as a result of land restitution and agrarian reform are expected, with the slow pace of land claim resolution flagged as impacting negatively through non-use of productive agricultural land and thwarting strategic spatial planning efforts (Limpopo Province, 2016). Studies in the Vhembe District also show that, post-reform, inadequate extension services and financial support have led to dissatisfaction with the process (e.g. Mukovhe and Moyo, 2019). The prescribed production models, with community ownership not necessarily suited to large-scale production, means beneficiaries are unable to compete with established agribusiness

(Rusenga, 2020) and with negative impacts of restitution processes on productivity and the physical condition of farm properties (for example in the Luvuvhu catchment; Lahiff et al., 2012).

Future trends in agriculture in the EFTEON-SLL will likely follow those observed locally and nationally over the last two decades and this should be a key focus of environmental research informing developmental needs within a context of change, highly constrained natural resources and also accounting for the role of subsistence agriculture in sustaining livelihoods in the EFTEON-SLL (Walter *et al.*, 2020). While South Africa has a stable number of farming cadastres, sole proprietor farming declined by a third between 2007-2017 while farms run by private companies increased threefold in the same period, the latter without a concomitant increase in the labour force lost by the former. However, large farms (6.5% of farms nationally) contributed 51% to total employment and 67% to total income (Statistics South Africa, 2018).

2.2. Spatial coverage of biomes and vegetation units

The EFTEON-SLL, with 16 vegetation units in three biomes, falls within the savanna biome overall (South African National Biodiversity Institute, 2006-; Figure 10). One unit, Gravelotte Rocky Bushveld, does not form part of the Soutpansberg Geomorphic Province and is included in the upper-Luvuvhu catchment.

Figure 10. Proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape detailing national vegetation units.

Table 1. Vegetation units and area (km²) by biome within the EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape.

Vegetation unit	Area km ²	Biome
Cathedral Mopane Bushveld	99	Savanna
Granite Lowveld	582	Savanna
Gravelotte Rocky Bushveld	15	Savanna
Ironwood Dry Forest	65	Forest
Limpopo Ridge Bushveld	217	Savanna
Lowveld Riverine Forest	2	Savanna
Makhado Sweet Bushveld	586	Savanna
Makuleke Sandy Bushveld	1 641	Savanna
Mopane Basalt Shrubland	20	Savanna
Musina Mopane Bushveld	339	Savanna
Northern Mistbelt Forest	12	Forest
Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld	3 799	Savanna
Soutpansberg Summit Sourveld	62	Grassland
Subtropical Alluvial Vegetation	17	Azonal
Tzaneen Sour Bushveld	306	Savanna
VhaVenda Miombo	0.3	Savanna
Total	7 761	

While the national vegetation units are mapped at the broad scale with substantial disparities in grass and forest cover compared to other models, for example, National Land Cover data (see Figure 4), the total savanna component (11 of the 16 vegetation units) is ~7 604 km² or 98% of the landscape with the remaining 157 km² (an underestimate, see below) divided between forest, grassland and alluvial/azonal vegetation (Table 1). Three of the units are entirely contained within (endemic to) the EFTEON-SLL of which Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld, a complex mosaic of differing vegetation from open sandveld to moist thicket (Rutherford *et al.*, 2006; Mostert *et al.*, 2008), makes up 49%. Other units, for example Vhavenda Miombo are highly restricted and threatened (Tshisikhawe *et al.*, 2013) extending

over as little as 0.3 km², or highly fragmented such as Northern Mistbelt Forest which is mapped over 103 separate polygons, with substantial area disparity between the 2014 (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2015a) and 2018 landcover data (the latter much reduced and excluding extensive known high canopy forest patches). Sourveld grassland is found in the higher altitudes while Northern Escarpment Afromontane Fynbos is stated to occur on the summits, though is unmapped (Rutherford *et al.*, 2006).

2.3. Coupled terrestrial and aquatic systems

Figure 11. Flow cessation in the Luvuvhu River at Tshino in October 2016. Photograph: P. Ramulifho.

With several higher order rivers, some free-flowing, originating in the EFTEON-SLL and one bisecting it, the scaled transitions (environmental and natural to non-natural) characteristic of the landscape allow for spatio-temporal analysis of land-use and other anthropogenic pressures by river order, quaternary catchment (e.g. Bailey and Pitman, 2015), sub-catchment management area or SWSA and ground water resources, also incorporating climatic data. Studies incorporating streamflow and rainfall data show high risk and vulnerability to floods (with

significant and catastrophic consequence levels) and drought in the Vhembe District (e.g. Odiyo *et al.*, 2019). Understanding hydrological and other hazards in terms of human impact on coupled terrestrial systems should be a priority given, for example, substantial land transformation in the catchment of the Luvuvhu River

(Kundu *et al.*, 2015). River gauging stations (some discontinued) maintained (or otherwise) in the study area show marked declines in flow, particularly during the summer months and there is the opportunity to couple this to more detailed spatial analysis of catchments, for example changes to land cover/land-use over remote sensing time series, including historical aerial photography. The Luvuvhu River gauging station at Tshino (see section 4.2 for location and details of other flow gauges) has seen a particularly marked decline in flow volumes of this major river draining the study area. Figure 11 shows absence of any flow at Tshino in 2016 while Figure 12 shows annual flow by season over ~70 years and Figure 13 presents this same time series by month, further illustrating the decline in summer flow volumes.

Figure 12. Annual flow at Tshino (A9H0001), Luvuvhu River, over a 70-year period (1932 – 2005) in m³/s. The horizontal line represents the mean total annual flow. The y-axis represents the sum of daily flows (m³/s) over a one-year period.

Figure 13. Daily flow at Tshino (A9H0001), Luvuvhu River, shown by month over a 70-year period (1932 – 2005) in m³/s.

The Luvuvhu catchment has been the subject of fish and macroinvertebrate monitoring over the last 20 years (e.g. Angliss *et al.*, 2001; Foord and Fouche, 2016, Modiba *et al.*, 2017), providing comparative baseline data for future surveys. Recent studies are also focused on the development of indicator species of flow and temperature changes (Ramulifho *et al.*, 2020).

Apart from impacts on flow volumes, rivers and reservoirs in the EFTEON-SLL are contaminated by human activities with one study across 12 catchments in the Vhembe District finding poor microbial quality across most sampling sites, independent of seasonality, with both total coliform and *Escherichia coli* concentrations beyond Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS) limits and posing health risks to communities reliant on rivers (Traoré *et al.*, 2016). Equally, local groundwater resources are affected by effluents from agriculture, livestock, industry and households in the area with widespread contamination found by some studies (e.g. Potgieter *et al.*, 2006; Odiyo and Mukungo, 2018) with high concentrations of NO₃, *E. coli* and *Enterococcus faecalis* across seasons (Enitan-Folami *et al.*, 2019) within the Luvuvhu-Letaba Water Management Area where water supply for rural and urban populations takes the vast majority of abstracted groundwater (Water Research Commission, 2020). The major impoundments of the Luvuvhu river, the Albasini and Nandoni dams (with capacities of 28 and 166 million m³ respectively), have also been investigated with build-up of Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) (Barnhoorn *et al.*, 2009) and other endocrine disruptors (Barnhoorn *et al.*, 2010) have been shown for fish in the Nandoni and Albasini dams, the two largest impoundments of the Luvuvhu river.

2.4. Socio-ecological systems in a South African developmental context

With private and state-led conservation programmes, commercial agriculture and forestry, a rapidly growing rural population and proposed large-scale mining activities to the north, the landscape provides a microcosm for the study of socio-ecological systems in the context of future developmental pathways in South Africa.

Traditional knowledge

There is a large focus at UniVen on community-based research and social surveys are conducted to probe perceptions and increase awareness around sustainable resource use. For example, natural sacred sites (Zwifho) are widespread, culturally protected and a particularly important aspect of Vhavenda culture (with well-known examples in the EFTEON-SLL being Lake Fundudzi - the largest natural inland lake in South Africa formed from landslide erosion ~100 ka (Partridge and Scott, 2000)), the Thathe Vondo forest and Phiphidi waterfalls. Zwifho and traditional natural resource knowledge and the forces of change (e.g. urbanisation) influencing the continued acquisition and transmission of such knowledge are increasingly a focus for researchers given opportunities for integrating them into environmental restoration projects (Constant and Tshisikhawe, 2018; Constant and Taylor, 2020).

Agro-ecology

Under the UniVen SARCHI Chair, the German-funded SPACES II (SALLNet) project has demonstrated the substantial economic value of natural pest predators (e.g. birds and bats) and pollinators (bees and other Hymenoptera) to macadamia growers in the Luvuvhu valley. Experiments have further indicated the critical

importance of retaining natural habitat corridors in the landscape (Grass *et al.*, 2018; Weier *et al.*, 2018; Linden *et al.*, 2019). Studies in progress are assessing the impacts of climate change on macadamia pollination, pest control and production. Ongoing community engagements and social surveys amongst growers are identifying more ecologically sustainable farming practices to enhance both pest management and production. Also, under the UniVen SARChI Chair, researchers within the EcoRodMan project (African Union funded) have engaged local communities and schools to firstly assess the impacts of pest rodent damage to households and crops and secondly promote the value of natural avian (owls) and terrestrial (mongooses) as well as domestic (cats and dogs) predators in terms of biological control of rodent pests (Williams *et al.*, 2018).

Human-wildlife conflict

Human-primate conflicts (specifically with vervet monkeys (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*) and chacma baboons (*Papio ursinus*)) have been identified in subsistence and commercial farming areas in the eastern Soutpansberg (Linden *et al.*, in prep.) and some data on monkey crop damage has been collected in commercial macadamia orchards (Linden *et al.*, 2019). However, there is a need for more extensive study quantifying and qualifying human-primate conflicts including investigations of possible mitigation measures. Livestock (including domestic and game species) predation, in particular by leopards, is a concern in the matrix surrounding the conservation areas of the EFTEON-SLL with detrimental impacts on carnivore populations through poisoning and snaring (e.g. Chase-Grey *et al.*, 2017; Williams *et al.*, 2017) with ongoing mitigation projects in the western Soutpansberg including the use of livestock-guarding dogs. The agricultural areas of the eastern Soutpansberg have been a focus area of the StopRats project (in collaboration with UniVen), looking at rodent pests and crop damage, food contamination and disease transmission (e.g. Labuschagne *et al.*, 2016).

2.5. Opportunities to act as a National Research Infrastructure

The EFTEON-SLL has numerous well-developed and well-networked research programmes involving both national and international institutions and it provides a particularly strategic location and opportunity to act as a National Research Infrastructure. There is a very strong focus on cooperation and learning between multidisciplinary local and international researchers with emphasis on student training.

Since 1987, the University of Venda has been a leader in environmental research in northern South Africa, providing a platform for a large range of collaborations, with long-term sustainability assured. The University conducts research and trains students in a wide range of environmental and socio-ecological topics and has long-established relationships with various institutions both locally (universities of Kwa-Zulu Natal, Stellenbosch (Centre for Invasion Biology), Pretoria, Free State, Rhodes, Witwaterstrand and Cape Town and organisations such as the South African National Biodiversity Institute, Agricultural Research Council, Endangered Wildlife Trust, Vhembe Biosphere Reserve and Lajuma Research Centre) and globally (universities of Göttingen, Hohenheim, Utrecht, Durham, Greenwich and Hamburg). It has hosted two successful SPACES I Project ARS AfricaE, Limpopo Living Landscapes (2014-2018) and SPACES II (2018-

2022) (funded mainly by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)) projects linked to climate-change impacts on Limpopo landscapes, South African Limpopo Landscapes Network (NRF Biodiversity Chair) and Ecosystem Management Support for Climate Change in Southern Africa (Vuwani Science Resource Centre). The SARChI National Research Foundation Chair (Tier 1) on Biodiversity Value and Change at UniVen commenced in September 2013 and has a 15-year time frame (2013–2027). The Chair has published over 60 research articles and graduated 21 Honours, 21 MSc and 13 PhD students.

Additionally, other relevant research and conservation organisations in the EFTEON-SLL are well networked with UniVen and each other as well as adding their own specific associations, for example the robust coordination between the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, UniVen, local government and provincial and national government sector departments. The development of the SANBI Thohoyandou National Botanical Garden (MoU signed with UniVen), with the garden acting as a biodiversity centre with research facilities, has strong synergy with UniVen and EFTEON, linking the roles of a botanical garden to socio-ecological systems and change over the broader landscape and human population.

3. Landscape location in the face of global change

Interpretation of patterns predicted under future climate change and current and future atmospheric CO₂ concentrations is informed by the palaeoecological and historical record, with emphasis on human impacts. For example, palynological studies of pollen spectra from peat wetlands in the eastern Soutpansberg concur largely with regional evidence showing mainly grassland and fynbos elements circa 10 000 years BP, increasing savannah elements circa 10 000–6 500 years BP, an increase in mesic woodland elements until 1 500 years BP where there is a sharp decrease in tree pollen, likely attributable to burning and clearing by Iron Age people recently moved into the area (Scott, 1987). Although increased fire cycles as a result of burning by Iron Age peoples is debated and was possibly localised (e.g. Scott, 2002; Breman *et al.*, 2012) the role of fire in shaping biome distribution is clear (e.g. Bond *et al.*, 2003).

The historical record of the EFTEON-SLL illustrates large-scale and short-term anthropogenically-induced shifts in vegetation and faunal assemblages (e.g. extirpation of elephant populations and large-scale timber (e.g. *Afrocarpus falcatus*) harvesting (Plug *et al.*, 2000) and biome shifts (Hahn, 2018)), contemporary deforestation (Munyati and Kabanda, 2009), intensifying land transformation and habitat fragmentation (e.g. Linden, 2020; Walter *et al.*, 2020), altered hydrology (Bailey and Pitman, 2015) and the emergence of biologically invaded (novel) ecosystems (Richardson *et al.*, 2020). While data on intensity and extent of biological invasion is lacking, the intensive agri- and silvicultural areas on the mesic southern slopes of the central and eastern Soutpansberg are particularly affected by invasive alien plants (IAPs) such as *Lantana camara*, *Chromolaena odorata* and *Senna* spp., especially in lower catchment areas, while *Acacia* and *Eucalyptus* spp. tree invasions characterise the upper reaches. Over 120 IAPs are recorded for the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve area falling within the moist subtropical- and semi-arid invaders zones in turn corresponding with mesic Savanna distribution (Richardson *et al.*, 2020).

The contemporary landscape, derived from these (increasing) anthropogenic pressures, is the status quo in the face of global change.

3.1. Presence of near-natural representative land cover and modified land uses

The EFTEON-SLL comprises mostly natural land-cover (although see Hahn, 2018) with the Limpopo Conservation Plan (Table 2; Figure 7; Desmet *et al.*, 2013) indicating ~20% (1 629 km²) of the total area of 7 761 km² as having been completely transformed, the remainder comprising critical biodiversity areas, natural areas, (natural) ecological support areas and protected areas with levels of autonomous ecological process.

Table 2. Limpopo Conservation Plan categories of the EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape by area (km²) and percentage. Note that Ecological Support Area 2 comprises transformed land (Desmet *et al.*, 2013).

Category	CBA	Area (km ²)	Percent
Critical Biodiversity Area 1	CBA1	2 896	37
Critical Biodiversity Area 2	CBA2	1 133	15
Ecological Support Area 1	ESA1	867	11
Ecological Support Area 2	ESA2	1 385	18
No Natural Remaining	NNR	244	3
Other Natural Area	ONA	258	3
Protected Area	PA	978	13
		7 761	

The 2018 National Land Cover data (20 m resolution; Department of Environmental Affairs, 2018) applied to the EFTEON-SLL shows the area encompassing largely natural areas (e.g. 71% natural woodland and forest) over 54 land cover classes of which 16 are natural and the remainder anthropogenic, reclassified to 11 classes for simplicity in Figure 4 and Figure 14 (below).

Figure 14. Land cover (reclassified for simplicity to 11 classes) and percentage part of the EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape. South African National Land-cover (Department of Environmental Affairs 2018).

3.2. Projected climatic impacts

Trends in Africa suggest the continent may experience double the global rate of warming (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2018b), with clear increases in average temperatures already measured across southern Africa (Kruger and Nxumalo, 2017) and tropical southern Africa being one of the fastest warming areas (projected rises of 2 – 4 °C in the interior) with likely increases in already high evapotranspiration (e.g. Van Niekerk *et al.*, 2018) and extreme events such as drought and heavy rainfall events (Davis-Reddy and Vincent, 2017). Rainfall predictions for southern Africa are ambiguous with no consensus on wetting and drying trends (Foden *et al.*, 2019) though historical data (1921–2015) show drying trends across north-eastern South Africa (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2018b).

Overall, biome shifts are likely across the EFTEON-SLL with a high probability of grasslands (Soutpansberg Summit Sourveld, endemic to the mountain) disappearing under most scenarios (e.g. Driver *et al.*, 2012; Moncrieff *et al.*, 2015) with increases in woody cover (currently observed; Hahn, 2018; Foden *et al.*, 2019), exacerbated biological invasion and transition to savanna (exactly how is debated given complex feedbacks between climate, CO₂, fire and C₄ grasses; Engelbrecht and Engelbrecht, 2016) and forest (e.g. Moncrieff *et al.*, 2015) with development of a tropical environmental zone in the north and east under all representative concentration pathways above 1.9 (Metzger *et al.*, 2013) and shift of the study area to arid desert or steppe, hot, under Köppen-Geiger climate zones in a 2°C or 3°C warmer world (Engelbrecht and Engelbrecht, 2016).

Strong contemporary climatic gradients and the influence of geomorphology in the EFTEON-SLL allow for optimal opportunities for observation of climate change impacts at various scales across multiple physical (e.g. altitudinal), ecological and anthropogenic transitions as part of deliberate, planned data collection (Foden *et al.*, 2019). The strong east-west and north-south elevational gradients provide an ideal landscape within a manageable study area to monitor and predict the impacts of climate change (Figure 15). An existing 12 year transect across the western Soutpansberg is based on this premise (Munyai and Foord, 2012; Bishop *et al.*, 2019) and local niche models agree that fragmented high-elevation grassland ecosystems in the Soutpansberg are threatened by climate change and/or bush encroachment (Taylor *et al.*, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Hahn, 2018). Baseline data exists in the study area for populations of a number of specialised (e.g. largely restricted to higher altitude zones of regular cloud immersion, “mistbelt”, or forest/grassland specialists) endemic or relict taxa with the potential to act as early indicators of species/community/biome changes and help predict coming broader scale impacts. Such surveys, of cloud-dependent biota (taxonomic and functional composition of plant communities) for example, may provide an estimation of cloud base heights and allow for detection of change over time (e.g. Hulshof *et al.* 2020). Examples of range-restricted species include *Aloe vossii* (Hahn, 2000), *Vhembelacerta rupicola* (Kirchhof *et al.*, 2010a; Kirchhof *et al.*, 2010b), *Lygodactylus soutpansbergensis* and *L. incognitus* (Petford *et al.*, 2019) and the highly localised *Kalanchoe crundallii* (Smith and Hahn, 2019)) while certain species are in urgent need of local census such as the Endangered mountain reedbeek.

Figure 15. Three north-south profiles across the Soutpansberg from west to east at Lejuma (A), centroid of the Soutpansberg (B) and Tshamavudze (C); Distribution of the Soutpansberg trigonometric beacons by longitude with a linear regression approximating the east-west inclination (D). The Blauwberg beacon (excluded from the linear regression) was included to illustrate the relationship of this inselberg to the Soutpansberg. From: Hahn, 2011.

3.3. Transition zones between biomes

Savanna – forest - grassland transitions can be found across the mountain over different elevational and land-use transects allowing for experimental studies, also across the 12 different vegetation units forming the savanna biome in the study landscape (Figure 10). Bush encroachment/invasion of grasslands is typical for extensive areas of the central-southern slopes on basaltic soils and although this is largely mapped as being within the Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld (savanna) unit it can be considered a novel ecosystem most resembling thicket (Hahn, 2018) and, given other studies, possibly succeeding to forest (Bond *et al.*, 2003) in line with (particular) models for biome shifts by 2100 (Moncrieff *et al.*, 2015). Biome shifts in large areas of degraded land (including communal landscapes, deforested areas and mesic areas with intensive invasive alien plant infestation) will be more challenging to predict, although coupled monitoring of large areas of conserved land may inform observation of change processes here.

3.4. Expected developmental pathways for the region

Broadly, probable developmental pathways for the EFTEON-SLL and region will mainly be urbanization in the east, commercial agriculture in the south, conservation in the far west and far east (Greater Kruger Strategic Development Programme, 2020) and mining in the north. They are underpinned by the recognition of under-development and lack of services in the rural areas. Limpopo strategic spatial and sector plans emphasise agriculture as a pivot for rural economic transformation, with mining and tourism highlighted as additional economic foci, the potential for the Information and Communication Technology sector to drive integrated rural development, promotion of rural-urban links and noting that Vhembe District in particular is strategically located for access to African markets (Limpopo Province, 2016; Department of Rural Development and Land Reform, 2016). The Vhembe District Municipality Integrated Development Plan (IDP) reiterates these foci as strategic opportunities for development, also emphasising the link between tourism and heritage (Vhembe District Municipality, undated).

Developmental pathways in the Vhembe District are potentially competing (Vhembe District Municipality, 2017) and there is a need for better spatial targeting of identified opportunities to avoid land use conflicts between sectors. While it is stated in the Limpopo Province Spatial Development Framework (SDF; Limpopo Province, 2016) that the province's protected area network can and should be expanded to incorporate unprotected critical biodiversity areas, the plan also emphasises expansion of silviculture in the Soutpansberg and the need for the development of the designated Musina-Makhado Special Economic Zone (SEZ; Republic of South Africa, 2016; Figure 16) and potential and actual extraction of coal, diamond, copper and platinum group minerals within a proclaimed (2009) UNESCO biosphere reserve, itself based on principles of sustainable development. Both of these opportunities would infringe upon critical biodiversity areas and exacerbate a key weakness identified in the SDF, that of widespread water scarcity coupled with water-intensive resource-based sectors (Limpopo Province, 2016). Within, adjacent and to the north of the EFTEON-SLL impacts of the SEZ development may include negative effects on air quality and increased abstraction (with potential for extensive aquifer dewatering) of stressed water resources with coalfields in

particular being highlighted as a potential threat to SWSAs (Le Maitre *et al.*, 2018). The bulk water requirements for the Musina-Makhado SEZ southern site alone are estimated at 13 911 km³ over the 9-year construction period (Delta Built Environment Consultants, 2020).

Figure 16. Proposed Soutpansberg Landscape EFTEON study area indicating protected areas, coal projects and Musina-Makhado Special Economic Zone cadastres

Based on 2011 census results (Statistics South Africa, 2012), the two local municipalities which make up the majority of the EFTEON-SLL, Makhado and Thulamela, are home to more than 1.1 million people. Some of the largest municipalities, e.g. Nelson Mandela Municipality, (ranked 6th in SA) are smaller than this. Around 65% of people are young, < 35 years old, and the unemployment rate of youth varies between 50 (Makhado) - 58% (Thulamela) (Statistics South Africa, 2012). While 85% of people have access to electricity, only 15% have piped water inside their dwellings. Unemployment and the absence of services increases dependence on local resources through, e.g. poaching, fuel wood collection, unsustainable subsistence agriculture, wetland drainage, illegal sand mining or support for destructive open cast coal mining projects. With a population growth rate of between 0.43 and 0.68%, these pressures are predicted to increase.

Both the municipalities have a current (2019-2022) IDP (linked to SDFs) with an emphasis on development of agriculture (including irrigation schemes), land claims and service delivery including housing and electricity provision and a strong focus on water provision. Peri-urban development and agriculture transforming land, direct use of natural resources and constrained water resources are key issues in the EFTEON-SLL study

area and successful strategies to address these pressures can be informed by EFTEON quantification of them.

Figures from the municipal IDPs provide insight into necessary developmental pathways and anticipated changes in land and resource use. For example, concerning peri-urban development transforming land, in 2018/19 3 117 stands were demarcated for housing in Thulamela amid a housing (provision) backlog of 22 000-27 000 units between 2016-2018 while Makhado lists a housing backlog of ~16 000 units. Concerning direct reliance on natural resources Makhado has 48 000 households which use electricity for cooking and 82 000 reliant on wood; Thulamela has 50 000 households which use electricity for cooking and 105 000 are reliant on wood (Makhado Municipality, undated; Thulamela Municipality, undated).

Makhado municipality recognises water as the scarcest natural resource and links this and other development issues to the fragmentation of residential development and costly, inefficient need for duplication of services (which can be related back to the administrative history of the area). With differing figures provided for Thulamela (population 497 237) of ~54 000 households still reliant on rivers, streams and springs and 64 000 communities without access to water infrastructure, the Vhembe District budgeted ~360 million rand (2019-2020 financial year) for development of water infrastructure within Thulamela including five borehole drilling projects. With a water provision backlog of 31% of the population of ~417 000, the district budgeted a similar amount (~360 million rand; 2016-2018 budget years) for bulk water supply (33 projects 2017-2022) within Makhado, but also including a bulk pipeline from the Luvuvhu to the Middle Letaba River system in the Collins Chabane local municipality (Makhado Municipality, undated; Thulamela Municipality, undated).

4. Logistical and operational suitability of the core and associated sites

4.1. Security of tenure for the operations

This would be a flagship institutional project under the NRF SARChI Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve which is based at the University of Venda. The Vuwani Science Resource Centre is already a flagship University initiative. UniVen is a Historically Disadvantaged University that has long-term commitment to community engagement, research and training.

The university was established in 1982 and currently has more than 16 000 registered students. It is the largest research institution in far northern South Africa and the majority (> 90%) of the student population comes from local areas. Undergraduate and postgraduate qualifications include Agriculture, Business, Education, Law, Human Sciences, Natural Science, and Environmental Science. Chair facilities include seven offices as well as six postgraduate cubicles. All of these facilities have internet access while telephones are restricted to offices. The chair also has access to a further 12 postgraduate cubicles in the Department of Zoology. The Life Sciences building is a state-of-the-art research facility with chemistry, biochemistry and

microbiology departments. The Chair has one designated laboratory and access to a second. There is also a large 'dirty' laboratory in the Life Sciences building with vehicle access.

Figure 17. School of Mathematical and Natural Sciences, Life Sciences laboratory and entrance to "dirty" laboratory underneath the building, University of Venda

Figure 18. Facilities and office space in the SARChI Chair for Biodiversity Value and Change in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, Life Sciences building, University of Venda.

4.1.1. Vuwani Science Resource Centre

Vuwani Science Resource Centre operates as a community flagship of the University of Venda and would function as a core site for the EFTEON-SLL. The centre has 24-hour security personnel and there are several facilities, including an eddy covariance (EC) flux tower, a 5-kW photovoltaic system, mini weather station under the Southern African Universities Radiometric Network (SAURAN) programme and comparison photovoltaic systems between coastal and inland climate conditions. The centre has three laboratory spaces which are used for hands on experiments for secondary school learners, and a computer laboratory to train communities in basic computer skills. Apart from the laboratories the centre has a mini hall and exhibition

Figure 19. Infrastructure at the Vuwani Science Resource Centre. Clockwise from top left: Eddy Covariance Flux tower, SAURAN station, the premises photographed from the tower and 5 kW PV plant.

area with adjacent offices.

The centre has hosted both national and international activities. For science communication the centre hosts the national science week, Astrolab competitions, and Saturday Schools. It has also hosted an International Winter School on 'Eddy Covariance Flux Measurements' in 2019 (in collaboration with SAEON, the Thünen Institute, and SASSCAL), and the SAASTEC Annual Conference 2020 as well as renewable energy workshops for educators in Vhembe District.

In summary, Vuwani Science Resource Centre is ideally located to answer the questions related to land use change, climate-smart agriculture, the carbon cycle and greenhouse gas fluxes. The intention is that the centre as a research platform shares measured data and facilitates the use of this and the infrastructure by national and international researchers to support mitigation and adaptation to climate change in South Africa.

4.1.2. Endangered Wildlife Trust, Medike, Sand River

The EWT owns two properties, known as Medike, which straddle the Sand River gorge and stretch eastwards from there. The properties offer accommodation for up to 18 people and have a team of trained rangers on site who assist with ongoing data collection and monitoring. Linked to this is a trail camera monitoring network (an extension of the monitoring system on Lajuma Research Centre in the Luvhondo Nature Reserve) that

provides a baseline of biodiversity sightings data. The Medike site is earmarked for future conservation status and the EWT are spearheading an extensive Biodiversity Stewardship programme in the western Soutpansberg, involving private landowners and communities, based on this investment in conservation property. Medike is directly bordered by recently established Communal Property Associations (CPAs) and it can be seen as a microcosm of the conservation challenges faced in the wider area. Medike is directly confronted with intensive illegal sand mining in the Sand River (despite that section being classed as largely natural; Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, 2011), large-scale poaching of plant and animal species and is in the frontline of local human-wildlife conflicts. Medike showcases the critical need for community engagement and highlights the ever-increasing challenges of meeting people's developmental needs while trying to protect biodiversity in the face of increasing biological resource use.

Figure 20. Mining in the Sand River near Medike, Endangered Wildlife Trust staff interviewing a suspected poacher and conducting rail ecology studies. Photographs: O. van Schalkwyk.

4.1.3. Agricultural and silvicultural sectors

Ongoing agro-ecological research is conducted by UniVen across large-scale commercial agricultural concerns in the Luvuvhu catchment and with small-scale farmers in the traditional authority areas. A number of the commercial operations, including silvicultural, are involved with long-term environmental monitoring, recording climatic and hydrological variables. Key stakeholders in previous, current and envisaged future research projects include the Macadamia Growers Association (local members), the Molozi Trust and ZZ2. Komatiland Forests (South African Forestry Company Limited) estates (Thathe Vondo and Entabeni; containing designated Forest Nature Reserves) are a regular venue for UniVen research projects and the company has made data, including fine-scale plantation units and habitat mapping, available for this. Rivers in Komatiland estates are a venue for UniVen South African Scoring System (SASS) river health training and evaluation.

4.1.4. Lajuma Research Centre, Luvhondo Nature Reserve

Lajuma provides field research and educational opportunities informing conservation of the Soutpansberg region *sensu lato*. A well developed and equipped field site, it enhances the logistical and operational suitability of the EFTEON-SLL core and associated sites. It is one of six properties forming the 4 232 ha Luvhondo Nature Reserve (proclaimed 2014; Limpopo Province, 2014) in the far-western Soutpansberg. Operational since 2000, Lajuma is linked to international and South African universities (in particular UniVen) and conservation organisations with two main functions: hosting long term researchers in a wilderness venue and, hosting university and conservation groups for shorter-term research and training programmes. Lajuma facilitated research and sampling has led to substantial and annually increasing ecological knowledge and resultant academic output including 21 PhD degrees, over 60 MSc and Honours degrees and 88 peer-reviewed publications, considerably adding to the local scientific knowledge base and skills development. Lajuma hosts between 60 and 80 students, researchers and faculty and 12 to 14 groups with over 200 participants per annum. From 2017 through 2019 Lajuma annually reached ~280 participants from 18 countries and 21 academic institutions.

Figure 21. Activities at Lajuma Research Centre. *Inventorying bat species, transecting for spiders, attending a workshop, film crew and micro-biologists at work, sampling for aquatic invertebrates.*

A workshop and training facility, with presentation facilities, accommodates and caters for up to 35 people and two 14 bed camps are available to longer-term researchers as are a number of stand-alone residential units. Accommodation is equipped with solar voltaic electricity, hot showers, indoor and outdoor cooking facilities, fridges/freezers and wireless internet. Scientific resources including professional on-site scientific assistance, supervision and training, databases and weather records; small mammal traps, scouting cameras, dissecting microscopes, scales and GPS units are available. A 40-camera grid is in permanent

operation on Luvhondo to monitor mammal diversity and density and a more extensive camera grid operated by Durham University monitors large carnivores across the far-western Soutpansberg.

Lajuma staff were instrumental in the proclamation of the Luvhondo Protected Area and on the regional scale the UNESCO Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, underpinning these conservation achievements with a scientific basis. Lajuma staff undertake conservation planning, input into regional spatial plans and assess national Red List species (e.g. Linden *et al.*, 2016; Swanepoel *et al.*, 2016). Working with local scientists and conservationists, research and networking facilitated by Lajuma has highlighted the importance of the conservation of the western Soutpansberg unlike any other initiative. Lajuma has utilised this research in local and regional conservation projects, as well as training underprivileged South African students for whom funds are raised. Early research publicising leopard populations and inventorying fauna and flora has scaled to numerous long-term projects including annual leopard population monitoring by Panthera and the development of the Durham University Primate and Predator research and outreach programme with three full time Durham University staff members resident at Lajuma.

4.1.5. Provincial Nature Reserves

The Limpopo Department of Economic Development; Environment and Tourism (LEDET) is responsible for the management of Provincial Nature Reserves within the EFTEON-SLL including Happy Rest, Studholme, Nwanedi and Mphaphuli Cycad Reserve. These properties are widely distributed across the Soutpansberg with strong altitudinal gradients and, particularly in the case of Mphaphuli and Nwanedi, play important roles in conserving catchment areas of the Luvuvhu and Nwanedzi rivers and tributaries.

4.2. Existing facilities for hydrological observations

Data deterioration in rainfall records, streamflow gauging and reservoir records is a huge challenge for South Africa in the face of global change with, for example, a peak of over 2 000 rainfall stations in water management areas nationally in the 1970s declining to ~750 by 2010 (Bailey and Pitman, 2015). Within the EFTEON-SLL there are currently 17 gauging stations in the Luvuvhu catchment, five in the Nzhelele catchment, and three in the Sand River with six of these having data for more than 20 years. Of the latter, the current status is not completely clear with only two still seemingly operational and focused on monitoring water releases from the Nandoni dam and Xikundu weir (Table 3), while gauges with longer term data (> 30 years) are not operational anymore e.g. A9H001 and other long-term operating gauges are in canals (e.g. A9H003). However, according to Bailey and Pitman (2015) there were nine gauging stations, 17 rainfall stations (as of 2010) and nine water quality monitoring stations (with 3 896 samples recorded from 1966-2013) in the Luvuvhu catchment which were usable (data) for the Water Resources of South Africa 2012 Study (www.waterresourceswr2012.co.za) as were reservoir records for the Albasini (e.g. from 1952), Vondo, Nzhelele and Luphephe dams in the EFTEON-SLL study area and this infrastructure remains.

Table 3. Selected gauging stations by sub-Water Management Area, with number, name, catchment area (km²) and data availability (years).

Sub-WMA	Station No.	Station name	Catchment (km ²)	Data available (years)
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H006	Livhungwa River @ Barotta	16	1961 - 2020
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H027	Lutanandwa @ Levubu Settlement	46	2002 - 2020
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H007	Lutanandwa River @ Levubu Settlement	47	1961 - 2000
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H028	Luvuvhu @ Nooitgedacht	607	2003 - 2020
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H012	Luvuvhu River @ Mhinga	1 758	1987 - 2020
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H005	Luvuvhu River @ Nooitgedacht	611	1946 - 2020
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H001	Luvuvhu River @ Tshino	902	1912 - 2006
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H013	Mutale River @ Kruger National Park	1 776	1988 - 2019
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H029	Mutale River @ Mutale Pump Station	329	2003 - 2020
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H004	Mutale River @ Thengwe	320	1932 - 2004
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H002	Mutshundudi River @ Chibase	96	1931 - 2000
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H024	Mutshundudi River @ Chibase Sibasa	51	1994 - 1999
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H025	Mutshundudi River @ Vredenburg	387	1995 - 2020
Luvuvhu-Mutale	A9H003	Tshinane River @ Ngudza	62	1931 - 2020
Nzhelele-Nwanedzi	A8H002	Mutamba River @ Bekaf	490	1937 - 1947
Nzhelele-Nwanedzi	A8H005	Mutamba River @ King's Kloof	128	1960 - 1976
Nzhelele-Nwanedzi	A8H003	Mutamba River @ Prince's Hill	132	1938 - 1942
Nzhelele-Nwanedzi	A8H001	Nzhelele River @ Kondoa	543	1932 - 1946
Nzhelele-Nwanedzi	A8H004	Nzhelele River @ Schuitdrift	855	1938 - 1947
Sand	A7H001	Sand River @ Waterpoort	7 703	1957 - 2000
Sand	A7H010	Sand River @ Waterpoort	7 712	2002 - 2019
Sand	A7H006	Sand River @ Zamenkomst	6 700	1947 - 1958

Groundwater monitoring resources are variable with the Limpopo Groundwater Resource Information Project (GRIP) data recording 2 454 boreholes of various kinds (e.g. submersible, mono or handpumps with various data availability) in the EFTEON-SLL of which 1122 are recorded as having no equipment and no power (<http://griplimpopo.co.za/>). UniVen has a strong groundwater research focus and studies in the EFTEON-SLL have monitored boreholes for yield, finding available data sets were not fully populated requiring field verification (e.g. Mukheli, 2018) or used testing boreholes to validate models (e.g. Makungo and Odiyo, 2017). A number of studies have nationally modelled and calibrated groundwater volumes, quality, recharge, exploitation potential and sectoral use building on decades of prior research (e.g. Water Research Commission, 2020) while other studies have used the GRIP dataset to accurately describe local hydrogeological conditions (e.g. du Toit *et al.*, 2012).

Figure 22. Proposed EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape indicating sub-Water Management Areas, current and historical stream gauging stations and rainfall stations in the study area and surrounds and boreholes within the study area recorded on the Limpopo Groundwater Resource Information Project database.

4.3. Suitability for the deployment of micrometeorological observations

The Vuwani Science Resource Centre hosts an EC flux measurement tower, under a collaboration between UniVen and The Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture (Germany). The tower was erected in 2016 as part of the project Adaptive Resilience of Southern African Ecosystems (ARS AfricaE; 2014-2018), and collaboratively maintained as one of the core research sites of the project EMSAfrica (Ecosystem Management Support for Climate Change in Southern Africa; 2018-2021) (www.emsafrica.org). The tower produces continuous measurements of the fluxes of CO₂, energy (shortwave and longwave) and water. The measurements will allow both international and national research communities to assess which climatic factors have a major role in affecting primary production and carbon uptake potential. The designation of the site as an EFTEON core will aid the long-term sustainability of the data collection.

The Vuwani site has been chosen to fulfil the assumptions of EC measurements, for example a large enough and representative footprint and absence of substantial advection. The footprint of this site (field of view) is several hectares (depending on local atmospheric turbulence) with the aim to measure CO₂ and energy fluxes (sensible and latent heat) in a peri-urban landscape consisting of residential area and scattered vegetation both being highly influenced by human activities. Few flux towers provide information on these kinds of

environments which makes the Vuwani site somewhat unique as the majority of existing EC towers are placed in natural environments.

While the Vuwani site represents a heavily human-modified environment with some livestock grazing, the measurements could be compared with a potential second EC tower in a natural area established as part of the EFTEON-SLL and be compared to the existing Phalaborwa/Malopeni EC tower in the Kruger National Park ~150 km south-east, representing a site with low human impact. These possibilities offer a unique comparison and an opportunity to observe the impacts of human management on carbon balance.

4.4. Long-term observations and experiments

Following are details on some existing long-term research and monitoring schemes across the Soutpansberg listed separately for the east and west.

4.4.1. Eastern Soutpansberg

Existing ambitious experiments include ecosystem services valuation via predator and pollination enclosure trials and biodiversity monitoring experiments in macadamia, mango and litchi plantations in the upper-Luvuvhu catchment in the eastern Soutpansberg (e.g., Grass *et al.*, 2018; Linden *et al.*, 2019). Under the auspices of the SPACES Limpopo Living Landscapes (LLL: 2013-2018) and South African Limpopo Landscapes Network (SALLnet: 2018-2022) projects (of which UniVen is a key partner), these experiments are coupled with studies on macadamia tree water use and socioeconomic surveys of macadamia farmers and communities from surrounding rangelands, ecological monitoring of rivers in the Luvuvhu catchment (using macroinvertebrates and fish health) and experiments undertaken at the UniVen Experimental Farm on crop diversification to mitigate climate change. In addition, transplant experiments and bush clearing experiments have been undertaken. Comparative studies have been undertaken along environmental gradients (pollination, meso-carnivore, dung beetles) and there are a large number of opportunities in the region for further experimental studies

Vuwani Science Resource Centre

The Vuwani centre hosts a mini weather station under the SAURAN programme which aims to make high-resolution, ground-based solar radiometric data available from stations located across the southern African region, including South Africa, Namibia, Botswana and Reunion Island. Most of the stations provide direct normal irradiance (DNI), global horizontal irradiance (GHI) and diffuse horizontal irradiance (DHI) at 1-minute, hourly and daily time averaged intervals, using state of the art Kipp and Zonen radiometers. The data collected at Vuwani Science Resource Centre has been used for different research purposes including honours and masters research projects. The facilities have a 5-kW photovoltaic plant which supplies electricity to the centre during the day and two solar panels which are used for performance comparison between the inland region (Vuwani Science Resource Centre) and coastal region (Nelson Mandela University).

The Vuwani centre hosts an eddy covariance (EC) flux tower the data of which are shared between project collaborating partners (including UniVen and SAEON) and on open-access databases, such as the SASSCAL Open Access Data Centre and Fluxnet. So far, due to technical limitations, limited flux data are available. The EMSAfrica project runs until November 2021 (with potential extension), and during this period, funds are reserved for the full maintenance of the tower and also for EC related training of EFTEON staff and researchers.

The transfer of the Vuwani EC tower to the South African greenhouse gas observations network, preferably in the context of EFTEON, is one of the central milestones of the EMSAfrica project, and a central part of its capacity building activities. Furthermore, the collaborators at the Thünen Institute are committed to the development of joint long-term research collaborations and facilitating the linkages between EFTEON and ICOS (Integrated Carbon Observation System).

In addition to the above listed measurements, different types of remote sensing data have been and are currently acquired over the Vuwani site as part of the EMSAfrica project. These data include multi-sensor and -temporal optical, radar and thermal infrared earth observation data from various satellite missions. A small number of airborne remote sensing data (e.g. historical aerial photographs) and elevation information (e.g. a digital elevation model) are also available. These data sets can provide the basis for investigating the status and dynamics of different land surface parameters in the Vuwani and Soutpansberg landscape, including spatially explicit and quantitative assessments of land cover and land use change. As with the flux data, the remote sensing data are openly accessible for collaborative use and will be shared via open-access databases. The EMSAfrica project is strongly supportive to share its data on a SAEON-hosted database.

4.4.2. Western Soutpansberg

A variety of monitoring programmes are taking place at the Lajuma Research Centre in the Luvhondo Nature Reserve and adjacent areas. This includes a long-term invertebrate survey (12 years; seasonal) across an altitudinal transect by Prof. Stefan Foord from UniVen, resulting in several peer reviewed publications and new species described (e.g. the Lajuma jumping spider, *Phintella lajuma*). Two decades ago Dr Ian Gaigher from the Lajuma Research Centre initiated long term predator (particularly leopard) monitoring by using camera traps and spot-pattern identification and primate research through habituating resident groups of samango monkeys, vervet monkeys and chacma baboons for ecological and behavioural research. Since 2012, a large-scale mammal-monitoring camera trap grid across the far-western Soutpansberg is funded and operated by Prof. Russell Hill from Durham University Department of Anthropology which also undertakes primatological and human-wildlife conflict research in the area under the Primate Predator Project with substantial academic output and publication (e.g. Chase-Grey *et al.*, 2017; Williams *et al.*, 2017). Through a community outreach programme this initiative also explores issues such as livestock predation by carnivores in the Soutpansberg, working with landowners on reducing losses, as well as an environmental education programme for local schools.

In 2019 Lajuma established a permanent mammal monitoring camera trap grid for the Luvhondo Nature Reserve through a collaboration with the United States based NGO Lengau which funds equipment and a

field assistant. Panthera has undertaken an annual leopard survey over ~200 km² in the western Soutpansberg for the last six years. Since 2013 a long-term project on greater and lesser bushbaby ecology, behaviour, physiology and health is being conducted from Lajuma in collaboration with Prof. Michelle Sauther and Dr Frank Cuzzo (principal investigators) from the University of Colorado (Phukuntsi *et al.*, 2020). In 2020 a long-term rodent transect was established in collaboration with Dr Guila Ganem from the University of Montpellier and the UniVen Chair to record rodent diversity and population dynamics. Long-term samango monkey roadkill (since 2012; Linden *et al.*, 2020) and distribution data (since 2009) is being collected on a continuous basis in the greater Soutpansberg area by Dr Bibi Linden as well as seed dispersal research (an extensive seed collection is maintained) investigating mutualistic relationships of mammals and forest plants (Seufert *et al.*, 2009; Linden *et al.*, 2015; Stringer *et al.*, 2020).

Phytosociological data has been recorded in the western Soutpansberg, for example ordination of 442 sample plots in the western Soutpansberg and adjacent Blouberg (Mostert, 2008) and ordination of 62 plots of 0.04 ha (including tree size, regeneration, stand density, basal area and diameter) in the Hanglip forest (Geldenhuys and Murray, 1993). Durham University has been recording regular phenology data in Luvhondo Nature Reserve since 2014 including vegetation plots and 480 individual trees (e.g. Parker *et al.*, 2020).

The Endangered Wildlife Trust (EWT) are running a number of conservation and monitoring programmes within the EFTEON-SLL, including and within the Soutpansberg Protected Area managed by Oldrich van Schalkwyk. Monitoring at the EWT Medike site on the Sand River and adjacent properties since 2017 includes counter-poaching (of fauna and flora) operations and provides insight into the scale of biological resource use in a previously unsecured conservation property. With 500 patrols conducted over ~4600 km removing 445 snares and 30 illegal fishing nets to date, over 160 trespassers were encountered including illegal plant collectors with >200 kg of material. Prior to EWT purchasing the Medike properties, illegal sand mining had damaged a substantial portion of the riverbed and banks including destruction of riparian vegetation. Extensive illegal sand mining continues upstream of Medike threatening water resources, aquatic biodiversity while exacerbating flood events and the spread of alien invasive plants (Figure 19).

The Wildlife and Transport Programme of the EWT is run by Wendy Collinson and is based in the EFTEON-SLL, working to reduce the negative impacts of transport infrastructure on wildlife with long term data collected in the region including experimental mitigation trials (e.g. Collinson *et al.*, 2015; Collinson *et al.*, 2017). A new focus has been on recording baseline information on the ecological impact (wildlife mortality data) of the 3.7 km of railway line that runs through Medike.

A third project in the Soutpansberg area being undertaken by Prof. Norbert Hahn is aimed at the conservation of the globally Endangered pepper bark tree (*Warburgia salutaris*) with a first phase aimed at understanding the local conservation status and geographic priorities for the species followed by conservation action including the formal proclamation of a conservation corridor in a known priority area and the clearing of alien invasive plants (20 ha to date) known to compete for key riparian habitat. The third phase will work with local communities to identify threats, guide sustainable harvesting practices and encourage and enable self-cultivation to reduce/avoid wild harvesting. Lastly, a comprehensive re-assessment of the global IUCN red listing for the species will be undertaken (the current assessment is almost 20 years old. The “collateral

benefits” of this project, with the pepper bark as an emblematic species, are potentially extensive given the high levels of endemism, diversity of threatened species and biodiversity importance of this mountain system.

4.4.3. Other projects and initiatives

Vhembe Biosphere Reserve and specialist network

The Vhembe Biosphere Reserve (VBR) has the potential to become an observatory for global change and mitigation. Inscribed by UNESCO in 2009, the VBR submitted its 10-year review to UNESCO in 2019. Supported by LEDET (which financially supports a Coordinator and Assistant) in its first 10 years, the VBR facilitated a Strategic Environmental Management Plan (SEMP) and has facilitated a number of demonstration projects and stakeholder workshops to encourage environmental sustainability and awareness within communities.

There is a great need in having a centralised spatial (Geographical Information System) data platform collating and integrating the long-term data on cultural and natural history of the landscape. To this end the UniVen SARChI Chair has developed a network of biodiversity specialists and designed a structure for a Biodiversity Information Management System (BIMS) for the VBR on a local server. However, the completion and wider sharing of this database would benefit greatly from the technical expertise that could be provided through EFTEON.

Herbarium Soutpansbergensis

Long-term botanical studies of the Soutpansberg flora conducted by Prof. Norbert Hahn, curator of the Herbarium Soutpansbergensis (ZPB), with emphasis on floristic diversity and endemism since 1993. The herbarium comprises ~4 000 specimens (including 10 type specimens) from southern Africa with 1 500 from the Soutpansberg. Botanically, the herbarium directly contributed to the publication of about 15 peer-reviewed articles, two theses and numerous technical reports on the rare, endangered and endemic flora of South Africa. The herbarium has ongoing collaborations with local and international scientists and houses a comprehensive archive of the historic biodiversity of the Soutpansberg area and relevant reference library. Various geodatabases are maintained and regularly updated, most noteworthy being the Herbarium Soutpansbergensis specimen database, vascular plant species lists of the Soutpansberg and inventories of regional endemic species.

African Institute for Conservation Ecology

Dr Lourens Swanepoel (UniVen) directs this non-profit with various projects across the EFTEON-SLL and region including camera trapping grids with a focus on carnivore ecology and conservation. Based at Nthakeni on the Mutale River, a current project investigates community led lion conservation through community facilitated research (community poaching monitoring, community camera trap monitoring). The Nthakeni research camp is also a strategic monitoring site for the Mutale River entering the Kruger National Park and feeding the Luvuvhu River.

4.5. Availability of office facilities

With infrastructure support from UniVen, the Chair has established a Biodiversity Centre that incorporates several offices and workstations for staff, postdoctoral fellows and postgraduates, a well-established zoology museum comprising natural history collections, displays and a research library, a seminar room and a dedicated GIS server. The Chair can offer offices or workstations for the four envisaged EFTEON scientists and technicians. This facility with its associated infrastructure will outlive the funding support of the NRF Chair beyond 2027 and continue to be a centre within the School of Mathematical and Natural Sciences, where the Chair is housed. The school has a large range of laboratories that include field-based ones (dirty) and more clinical microbial and chemical laboratories. Certain labs are currently not used or underutilised. The GIS Unit at UniVen provides expertise, software (e.g. ArcGIS) and long-term datasets (such as SPOT, Landsat and Worldview satellite imagery). Other study sites have various expertise, accommodation and research facilities as described in above. The road network in the landscape is reasonably well developed with paved and unpaved provincial and minor roads bisected by a national road. Certain roads within the mountainous areas, in particular access roads to potential subsidiary monitoring sites, require the use of a high clearance four-wheel drive vehicle especially in the wet season.

4.6. Availability of residential facilities, schools, hospitals and potential employment for spouses

Thohoyandou and Louis Trichardt are the regional centres and provide access to accommodation, potential employment, private and public hospitals and schools. Short- and long-term residential facilities are available at certain subsidiary sites as detailed above.

4.7. Partner institutions

The University of Venda has local and international networks and collaborations (see section 2.5) with academic and other research institutions. A list of collaborators from 10 research and conservation institutions/organisations is provided as Appendix I.

4.8. Security

Vuwani Science Resource Centre and the University of Venda employ 24-hour security guards. Main subsidiary sites listed are generally remote, crime free and have permanent staff presence.

5. Stakeholder analysis

Engagement with relevant authorities and resident groups

A long history of research in the region means that UniVen and associated sites have well developed networks of local stakeholders across professionals, community organisations, commercial farmers and other land custodians. In addition, the long involvement of UniVen staff in the VBR (including Board members and office bearers of the VBR NPC) has seen active participation in the development of those networks including provincial (particularly LEDET) and local government and the VBR membership (with strong UniVen representation at Annual General Meetings). UniVen and Lajuma staff were contributors to the Limpopo Conservation Plan, VBR SEMP (Strategic Environmental Focus, 2016), Vhembe Bioregional Plan and EWT Red List assessments. The VBR is represented at various district level workshops/land development forums (recently holding widespread stakeholder consultations for the UNESCO 10-year review report), has facilitated stakeholder meetings on numerous issues from biodiversity assessment to mining projects and was actively involved in public participation meetings around these and other impact assessments.

Letters of support

Letters of support for the proposed Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape, attached as Appendix 2, are included from the following university departments, schools and organisations.

Office of the Deputy Vice Chancellor: Academic, University of Venda.

Office of the Dean, School of Environmental Science, University of Venda.

Vuwani Science Resource Centre, University of Venda.

Department of Microbiology, School of Mathematical and Natural Sciences, University of Venda.

Department of Ecology and Resource Management, School of Environmental Science, University of Venda.

South African National Biodiversity Institute.

South African National Parks.

Vhembe Biosphere Reserve.

DSI-NRF SARChI Research Chair (Ecosystem Health), University of Limpopo.

Department of Environmental Sciences, University of South Africa.

Department for Earth Observation, Institute of Geography, Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena.

Research Group Micrometeorology, The Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture.

Dean of Research, Agricultural Faculty, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen.

Department of Anthropology, University of Durham.

Endangered Wildlife Trust.

ZZZ.

African Institute for Conservation Ecology.

Lajuma Research Centre.

Web pages

SARChI (NRF-DST) Research Chair on Biodiversity Value and Change: <https://vhembecosystem.org/sarchi/>

SALLnet – South African Limpopo Landscapes Network: <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/592566.html>

Southern African Science Service Centre for Climate Change and Adaptive Land Management: <http://www.sasscal.org/>

Vhembe Biosphere Reserve: <https://www.vhembecosystem.org/>

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Appendix I. List of collaborators

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Appendix II. Letters of support for the EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape

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21 September 2020

Dr Gregor Feig
EFTEON Manager
SAEON
NRF

Email: gregor@saeon.ac.za

Tel: 073-980-8164

Dear DR Feig

MANAGEMENT SUPPORT FOR PROPOSAL TO CONSIDER UNIVEN AS THE PLATFORM FOR AN EFTEON LANDSCAPE

The University of Venda is a regional leader in environmental and socio-ecological research and training. Established in 1982, with more than 16,000 registered students, it is one of the largest tertiary institutions in Limpopo Province and the majority (> 90%) of the student population comes from the Vhembe District. Undergraduate and postgraduate qualifications include Agriculture, Business, Education, Law, Human Sciences, Natural Science, and Environmental Science. Collaborative research at the University of Venda now includes several international interdisciplinary research programmes focused on stakeholder engagement.

If the University of Venda is selected to host an EFTEON landscape platform, the platform will constitute a flagship project under the University's SARChI Chair in *Biodiversity Value and Change in the Vhembe Biosphere*. It will provide an integrated platform for university-wide collaborative research. The SARChI Chair undertakes to provide office space, while

laboratory space (one clean and one dirty laboratory) will be provided by the Department of Zoology, in the School of Mathematical and Natural Sciences.

I am certain that the University of Venda and its network of associated researchers provide an ideal platform for EFTEON and that the initiative will bring great benefits to our area. The benefits will accrue not only to the researchers, but also to decision makers at all levels of local and provincial government, through informing science-based planning. Data-driven and scientific evidence-led decision making has become more important than ever, given the challenges of socio-economic development for our communities and the numerous pressures on our natural environment. A local EFTEON platform has the potential to be a key resource in the District Development Model soon to be implemented by National Government.

The management of the University of Venda pledges its full support for this proposal. Any enquiries in this regard can be directed to my office.

Yours sincerely

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'JE Crafford', written in a cursive style.

Prof JE Crafford

DVC Academic

28 September 2020

Attention: EFTEON selection panel

c/o Dr Gregor Feig

Dear Sir/Madam,

Re: Letter of Support for “Soutpansberg Luvuvhu Landscape Proposal” to EFTEON

University of Venda, School of Environmental Sciences and its elaborate network of associated academics and researchers provide an ideal platform for EFTEON to carry out scientific research that has sustainable socio-economic benefits in the Soutpansberg Mountainous area within the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve. The proposed research on the Soutpansberg Luvuvhu Landscape has a huge potential to provide data that will provide the basis for making decisions that support sustainable utilisation and management of the rich natural resources in the region. Thus, science based planning will promote judicious and sustainable utilisation and management of natural resources for socio-economic development of the surrounding communities, considering the numerous pressures on our environment that would be possible to quantify scientifically.

The Departments of Hydrology and Water Resources, Mining and Environmental Geology, Ecology and Resource Management, Geography and Geoinformation Sciences and Urban and Regional Planning within the School of Environmental Sciences do extensive research and training across the proposed landscape focusing on the Nzhelele and Luvuvhu River catchments. The research that has been done in the landscape include water pollution research, development of indigenous technologies for solving water quality problems, wastewater quality and management, hydrological modelling and climate change adaptation, hydrological hazards (floods and droughts) and their impacts on livelihoods and socio-economic development, groundwater quantification and monitoring, land use management, soil erosion and gully development, among others. One of the major challenges that research has faced is inadequacy of data due to inadequate data monitoring systems such as flow gauges and boreholes. Operating and well maintained flow gauges and groundwater monitoring points are necessary to provide reliable long term data particularly for validation of hydrological and climate change models. The Departments in the School of Environmental Sciences would thus be available to utilise and maintain any monitoring system availed by EFTEON through the current proposed research initiative. The monitored long term data will promote research and postgraduate training as students will be able to apply them in validation of hydrological and hydrogeological modelling and for studies on long term monitoring of degradation and conservation of the natural environment.

The expanded monitoring within the landscape will contribute to better understanding and prediction of natural resources, hydrological and climate modelling to high or improved resolution, development of alternating water sources including groundwater and rainwater harvesting, prediction and preparedness towards extreme events, land degradation and management, biodiversity economy, etc. These will form the basis of new research questions amongst others.

Yours Sincerely,

Prof. J.O. Odiyo

University of Venda

To whom it may concern

RE: Letter of Institutional Support

Vuwani Science Resource Centre is a community outreach flagship under the University of Venda, currently host the EMSAfrica tower for (Ecosystem Management Support for climate change in Southern Africa) Eddy Flux measurement, under a collaboration between South African and German research institutions. As this is a three year collaboration, EFTEON is needed to take over and continue with the Long term measurements of different environmental parameters. The EMSAfrica collaboration has started from the ARS AfricaE collaboration which was focusing on the establishment of research infrastructures to measure ecosystem fluxes of greenhouse gases in parts of South Africa; Thus there is a need to expand the infrastructure available at Vuwani Science Resource Centre to long term measurements of different components of the ecological systems, terrestrial systems and parameters, water, soil and weather parameters.

The flux tower is intended for long term continuous operation and to provide long term environmental data for the national and global research community. The site currently measure the energy fluxes and CO₂ fluxes. The main aim is to compare the ecological eco systems caused by human activities and animals. The tower is currently focuses on the grazing land and human settlement area. We hope that the data collected from this tower will help the researcher to understand the long term ecological system changes.

The centre has mini hall, exhibition space, three laboratories, three office and a computer lab. There is 24 hour personnel security and several research stations around the centre, like the 5 kW PV system, Mini Weather station under the SAURAN network and comparison PV systems between the coastal and inland climate conditions. The operation of the EFTEON research station will be supported by the university of Venda and all activities are at the centre are reported to the school board of Mathematical and Natural Sciences which then report to both community engagement directorate and deputy vice chancellors academic office for university the entire university.

I would like to express strong support of the Vuwani Science Resource Centre for the proposal titled "Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape" submitted to the Department of Science and Technology: the Expanded Freshwater and Terrestrial Environmental

Dr. NE Maluta

Date: 29 September 2020

University of Venda

University of Venda

DEPARTMENT OF MICROBIOLOGY

03 September 2020

To Whom It May Concern

Re: LETTER OF SUPPORT FOR THE EFTEON PROJECT

Dear Madam/Sir

Over the past years, thanks to the General Water Lab set up by Prof N Potgieter in the Microbiology Department at the University of Venda, significant research projects commissioned by the South African Water Research Commission and the Wellcome Trust have been successfully completed. The Microbiology Department under the Laboratories of Prof N Potgieter and Prof AN Traore-Hoffman, will be looking at the microbial and chemical quality of environmental samples through boreholes and rivers.

The project proposed by Prof S Foord would allow experimentation to be conducted on a larger scale across the Vhembe Biosphere.

We bring our support to this grant application.

Prof AN Traore

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'AN Traore', written over a light blue rectangular background.

Prof N Potgieter

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'N Potgieter', written in a cursive style.

Thohoyandou, 10/09/2020

- TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN -

Re: letter of support from the Department of Ecology and Resource Management

In this letter I represent the department of Ecology and Resource Management in the School of Environmental Sciences, University of Venda. The department has a long history of research in the proposed landscape, as well as training young minds from the same area. Our research interests are quite wide ranging, encompassing ecosystem functioning and restoration, ecohydrology, biodiversity patterns and processes, impacts of invasive alien species, aquatic ecology, agroecology and environmental chemistry. Some examples of relevant research done in our department are the work done by Dr Dalu on plastic pollution in the Luvuvhu River system, by Prof Gitari on purification of fluoride laden groundwater in Siloam and by Dr Stam on rehabilitation after open cast coal mining in Mpumalanga. We consider ourselves to be very fortunate to have been invited to contribute to the bid to the EFTEON programme, as it offers excellent opportunities for long term research and training of our students.

Some of the research opportunities we hope to explore within EFTEON are the longer term impacts of woody encroachment on water resources as well as land use patterns, population pressure impact on land degradation, effects of socio-economic as well as cultural drivers on natural resource use (and abuse) and land degradation, effects of loss or reduction of ecosystem services on communities and ways to increase resilience of social-ecological systems to climate change effects and other environmental disruptions.

These topics require extensive long term monitoring of climatic, hydrological and ecological variables such as rainfall, evapotranspiration, stream flow, river sediment load, erosion, NPP etc. as well as socio-economic trends such as population growth, migration, demography, employment rate, education level, household incomes, reliance on natural resources, land used for subsistence or commercial agriculture, industrial and mining activity etc.

As a department we see the EFTEON programme as an excellent opportunity to expand our research into the above mentioned areas and we are therefore in full support of the initiative by Prof Foord and others to submit a bid.

Yours sincerely,

Dr EM Stam

University of Venda

10 September 2020

Prof. Stefan Foord
Department of Zoology
University of Venda
Private Bag X5050
0950

Letter of Support for UNIVEN Proposal: Soutpansberg Luvuvhu Landscape

On behalf of the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI), I would hereby like to offer our organisation's full support for the proposal from the University of Venda for the **Soutpansberg Luvuvhu Landscape** to be included in a national programme of the Department of Science and Technology: the Expanded Freshwater and Terrestrial Environmental Observation Network (EFTEON).

SANBI has an existing Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the University of Venda and is also managing the Thohoyandou Botanical Garden in Thohoyandou in the eastern Soutpansberg, as one of its national network of botanical gardens.

EFTEON as a highly networked National Research Infrastructure and regional observatory will assist the 89 ha Thohoyandou National Botanical Garden to develop its reach, linking the roles of a botanical garden to ecological-social systems and change over the broader landscape and human population.

With the garden acting as a biodiversity centre with research facilities, the data and products derived from EFTEON will provide a baseline for investigations in particular in collaboration with staff and students of the nearby University of Venda.

As a conservation garden, containing areas of natural savanna woodland (at the gardens and possible associated sites), the broader landscape monitoring function of EFTEON (meteorological, hydrological and ecological) will assist in management of the SANBI properties, adapting to and mitigating against effects of global change.

Developing a cultivated collection of indigenous plants unique to the Limpopo Province as well as incorporating traditional horticultural and agricultural sections, the environmental and sociological components of EFTEON will assist with research and conservation of extant populations linking to the garden's public information, interpretive and conservation roles, especially promoting biodiversity education to surrounding schools and communities.

Growing species representative of the regional vegetation types (including a variety of Soutpansberg endemic plants) a principle research question is the impact of future environmental change on these ecosystems and potential synergy with the garden experimenting with their horticulture in a different climatic zone.

A brief summary of SANBI's research involvement in the area to date

SANBI researchers have been involved in numerous entomological research projects with Univen MSc. and postdoc students in the area, through research into global change pressures on entomofauna – in particular effects of alien invasive vegetation, grazing, land use change and anticipated changes in climate (in altitude and changes in microclimate associated with vegetation change). This has produced 7 papers, all in journals with IF > 2.7.

SANBI staff have over the past several years been involved in biodiversity and entomological surveys in various parts of the Soutpansberg Mountain Range, including areas such as Lajuma, Mphaphuli Cycad Nature Reserve, and various other areas. SANBI is also involved in various projects associated with the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve. SANBI has made numerous seed collections from the Soutpansberg that have contributed to the Millennium Seed Bank Partnership, based at Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, UK.

SANBI horticulturists are currently involved in horticultural research involving various threatened tree species.

SANBI wildlife scientists have conducted collaborative research with Univen and the Lajuma Research Station in phylogenetics (phylogeography). In particular on species that include galagos and Samango monkeys for which no or limited genetic data is available that requires either taxonomic re-classification or identification of possible ecologically significant units (ESUs) or to identify cryptic species. In addition, capacity development has included co-supervision of PhD students registered with Univen and TUT.

How you will use the research infrastructure, in other words data made available by EFTEON.

These data will be particularly useful for assessing change in climatic variables that drive many of the patterns and processes in which we are interested.

General research questions that expanded monitoring across the local landscape will be useful in investigating.

Research questions of interest: how do land use change and climate change influence biodiversity and the ecological functions associated with it, in the area?

Yours sincerely

Christopher Willis

Chief Director: National Botanical Gardens
South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI)

To acquire and manage a system of national parks which represents the indigenous wildlife, vegetation, landscapes and significant cultural assets of South Africa for the pride and benefit of the nation.

Ref: EFTEON-29 September 2020
Contact person:
marisa.coetzee@sanparks.org

Attention Prof Stefan Foord
Department of Zoology
University of Venda
Private Bag X5050
Per email: Stefan.Foord@univen.ac.za

RE: Letter of support for UNIVEN proposal: Soutpansberg Luvuvhu landscape

Purpose

The South African National Parks Kruger National Park (SANParks-KNP) supports the University of Venda (UNIVEN) for the inclusion of the Soutpansberg Luvuvhu landscape proposal in the national programme of the Department of Science and Technology: the Expanded Freshwater and Terrestrial Environmental Observation Network (EFTEON).

Overview - SANParks Kruger National Park

The KNP was proclaimed on 2 September 1926 (Government Gazette No 1576 dated 2 September 1926), and is situated in the north-eastern corner of South Africa, bordering Mozambique in the east and Zimbabwe in the north. In compliance with NEM: PAA (57 of 2003), SANParks is required to develop a management plan for each of its protected areas. KNP Management plan serves as the key driving and reference document for the management and development of the park in its current and envisaged future form, with information on the background, biophysical context, desired state, programmes at strategic and operational levels and costing. The KNP Mission of the KNP is *“To conserve, protect and manage biodiversity, wilderness qualities and cultural resources, provide a diverse and responsible visitor experience, contributing towards social, ecological and economic resilience and well-being whilst strengthening constituency within a unique regional landscape.”*

The KNP Management Plan focuses on regional integrated land use integration over the next ten years and will seek to deliver on the Great Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area Treaty which, at its core, seeks to drive collective action in pursuit of resilient communities and ecosystems, whilst unlocking sustainable socio-economic benefits. To achieve this vision, the Management Plan can only be implemented through partnering with relevant sectors, organs of state, knowledge institutions, communities and NGOs. The strategic and operational programmes of the KNP are realised through the following High level objectives, and projects within these.

SANParks-KNP’s landscape based partnership commitment: Greater Kruger Strategic Development Programme

The Greater Kruger Strategic Development Programme (GKSDP) was developed in response to issues raised during consultation for the KNP Management Plan and the Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area Livelihood Strategy. It is based on an *integrated partnership model which recognises the integral relationship between natural capital (especially healthy functional ecosystems which deliver high quality services such as water) and socio-economic well-being (particularly for marginalised communities).*

The primary goal of the GKSDP is to provide a replicable landscape partnership prototype or “master” framework, which could be adapted by different protected areas relevant to their context, in support of conservation compatible land use outcomes. The GKSDP recognises the need, and seeks to leverage conservation as a key driver of the rural economy, making the explicit case for

addo elephant

agulhas

augrabies falls

bontebok

cape peninsula

golden gate highlands

karoo

kgalagadi transfrontier

knysna

kruger

marakele

mountain zebra

namaqua

tankwa karoo

tsitsikamma

richtersveld

vaalbos

vhembe dongola

west coast

wilderness

protected areas as a critical land use impacting on, and being interrelated with the diverse socio-ecological landscape within which it is embedded. The GKSDP provides a robust partnership framework, which is central to this programme. The GKSDP affords a methodology in which it contextualises the landscape through integrating strategic, natural capital, socio-economic, institutional, opportunity, and risk considerations, further guiding the partnership arrangements and entry points in a more focused manner.

Key anchor programmes identified through the GKSDP partnership

The following key programmes were identified within priority spatial areas, including that of the Soutpansberg Luvuvhu landscape: integrated catchment management (including SWSAs), integrated land use planning and scenario planning, protected area management effectiveness, protected area expansion/stewardship, securing ecosystems and species of interest, restoring the ecological infrastructure, climate change adaptation and mitigation, securing the ecological infrastructure, unlocking biodiversity and Responsible Tourism/green economies, strategic partnership arrangements from local to international level, innovative financing, research and knowledge transfer.

Soutpansberg Luvuvhu as landscape area of interest

The Vhembe region, in particular the Soutpansberg Luvuvhu landscape, was identified as a key strategic priority through GKSDP. SANParks-KNP will participate in initiatives that contribute to the following outcomes in collaboration with the GKSDP partnerships:

- Improve and maintain **healthy ecosystems** that promote responsible **biodiversity economies** through a range of **integrated land use** mechanisms and **sector programmes** within the protected area, local and district municipal, biosphere, bioregional and transboundary spheres.
- Implement meaningful interventions to address **climate change mitigation** and adaptation within vulnerable communities and sectors.
- Secure and improve ecosystem processes and associated **socio-economic benefits**, by re-connecting **ecological systems** and the inclusive expansion of the conservation estate, through a flexible range of stewardship models.
- Take a holistic management approach for **catchment and water resources management** in the catchments, to protect freshwater ecosystems whilst responsibly supporting the developmental water management potential of the resource.
- Mobilise **sustainable financing mechanisms** and institutional arrangements through the Greater Kruger Development Fund and other imperatives, in support of resilient wildlife economy, tourism and integrated land use programmes.
- **Strengthen institutional arrangements, policy development** and **knowledge transfer** in support of healthy ecosystems and resilient communities.

Whilst the Soutpansberg Luvuvhu landscape is noted for the biodiversity value in terms of endemism and ecosystems, it also forms part of UNESCO Biospheres, with its rich cultural heritage. It is also identified as Strategic Water Source Areas in terms of both the surface water and groundwater provisioning services. Notably there are a large number of riverine wetland systems that also contribute to this, particularly in the headwaters of the Mutale River. Presently a very low percentage of these regions are formally conserved or under some form of catchment stewardship. This presents a risk to the future water security and the benefits that can be gained from these areas under climate change vulnerabilities. This can significantly impact the socio-economies of the region and the freshwater ecosystems of the Great Limpopo Transfrontier Area (GLTFCA, Treaty 2002) and the Limpopo River Basin. Consideration needs to be given to strengthen partnerships and knowledge systems that can lead to the long term stewardship, ecosystem based adaptation and sustainable financing options of the region.

Partnership programmes supported by SANParks –KNP within this particular landscape

- Land use planning and management: protected area management and stewardship initiatives for a range of state, private and community areas within the project landscape
- Integrated catchment management: SWSA, participation in the GLTFCA transboundary water resource programmes, establishment of the Olifants Catchment Management Agency, water stewardship support, Makuleke Ramsar site monitoring and management
- Biodiversity economy programmes: wildlife management, responsible resource use
- Medicinal plant distribution and protection, in collaboration with community structures
- Species of interest management and monitoring: human-conflict, Threatened or protected plants (including but not limited to *Warburgia*), and wildlife species (e.g. elephant management, vultures)
- Ecological infrastructure restoration: invasive alien species management, land restoration through the Biodiversity Social projects and Limpopo Natural Resource Management programmes
- Reduction in environmental crime: participation in different International, National, Provincial and local safety and security clusters, including National Integrated Wildlife Management wildlife zones and institutional structures, Great Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area (GLTFCA) Pafuri-Sengwe Safety and Security node, the Provincial Joint Structures
- Livelihood programmes, e.g. those of the GLTFCA Pafuri-Sengwe node livelihood project, Biodiversity economy projects within the broader Makuya-Mutale region.
- Integrated land use and spatial planning, management and monitoring: inputs into Local and District Municipal Land use management schemes (LUMS), Spatial Development Frameworks (SDFs), Socio-economic development zones (Musina SEZ), land use transformation, ecosystem-based scenario planning.
- Participation in strategic partner platforms within the area: GLTFCA structures, Vhembe Biosphere, UNIVEN Research collaboration, GLTFCA Cooperative Agreement with protected areas open to KNP (including Makuya Nature Reserve, Makuleke Contractual Park), Traditional Healers medicinal plant distribution, KNP Community Forum, water use boards and forums, Flux towards
- SANParks Research Strategy and programmes: scientific and monitoring programmes informing strategic adaptive management, linked to the afore-mentioned and broader themes, including current monitoring through the flux towers.

Given the interest and involvement in research, monitoring, conservation and socio-economic programmes by SANParks within this landscape, we would be able to contribute to, and be guided by, the data generated by the EFTEON node in this landscape. The EFTEON node will support a range of decision-making and policy processes, including ecosystem-based adaption scenarios. SANParks-KNP strongly supports the selection of the Soutpansberg Luvuvhu landscape as an EFTEON node, and look forward to partnering with this initiative.

Yours sincerely

Dr M Coetzee
GM: Regional Integration and Planning
29.09.2020

Vhembe Biosphere Reserve NPC

Registered as NPC 2013/050303/08
C/o LEDET, Private Bag 5088
Thohoyandou 0950, South Africa
www.vhembebiosphere.org

email: makoni@vhembebiosphere.org

In association with:

09 September 2020

To whom it may concern,

Re: Letter of Institutional Support

I would like to express strong support of the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve (VBR) for the proposal titled “Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape” submitted to the Department of Science and Technology: the Expanded Freshwater and Terrestrial Environmental Observation Network. The proposal is well aligned to the VBR’s research objectives, which are:

- to conserve biodiversity and ecosystem services, including cultural and historic resources;
- to integrate conservation objectives with indigenous knowledge to promote equitable socio-economic development which is socio-culturally and ecologically sustainable;
- to provide research, monitoring, education and training opportunities and facilities for local, regional and worldwide purposes.

In the VBR, population growth coupled with land-use change (e.g., agriculture and urbanization) and climate change are placing increasing pressure on ecosystems and their ability to provide essential ecosystem services for human well-being.

Therefore, it is critical to understand how these drivers of ecosystem degradation, biodiversity and ecosystem services loss should be addressed to ensure the ongoing provisioning of these services and to avoid undue impacts on society. The data and the research outcomes from the proposed project will enable the VBR to manage and monitor ecosystems, biodiversity and ecosystem services, including the implementation of the necessary management interventions. The VBR would also

ensure that the VBR youth group and interested members of the community get capacitated to carry out long-term monitoring.

As the VBR, we propose that the project should also focus on the following research questions;

1. What is the level and impact of ecosystem services dependence in a rural-urban gradient?
2. Which ecosystem services are essential in a rural-urban gradient?
3. How do ecosystem services values based on different stakeholders' perspectives influence decision making in environmental issues?
4. What is the effect of traditional/indigenous knowledge on biodiversity conservation and ecosystem services supply?
5. What are the synergies and trade-offs between traditional/indigenous knowledge and scientific knowledge in the management of biodiversity and ecosystem services?
6. How can traditional/indigenous knowledge and scientific knowledge be integrated to achieve effective biodiversity conservation and ecosystem services enhancement?

The VBR will ensure that its board and staff members have sufficient time to engage with the project if successful.

Yours sincerely

Lutendo Mugwedi
VBR board chairperson

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'L. Mugwedi', enclosed within a hand-drawn oval shape.

University of Limpopo

Private Bag X1106, Sovenga, 0727, South Africa

Tel: (015) 268 2304, Fax: 0865169272, Email:Wilmien.Powell@ul.ac.za

30 September 2020

EFTEON panel members

RE: Support for EFTEON proposal

We have been doing research on Ecosystem Health, especially freshwater ecosystems and diversity of fish parasites, for more than 20 years in the Luvuvhu River System. These data have been sporadic and linked to availability of research funds, pots-graduate projects and researchers. By having long term monitoring programmes we will have access to quality long term data which will provide strategic answers to manage the Luvhuhu System in future, especially considering the effect of global change on biodiversity and ecosystem services. We thus strongly support the University of Venda with their application for an EFTEON node. The collaboration and provision of facilities and opportunities for research, training and education will be welcomed in the Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu landscape and essential research data will be generated, benefiting several stakeholders.

We wish UNIVEN all the best with their application.

Kind regards

Prof Wilmien Luus-Powell

DSI-NRF SARChI Research Chair (Ecosystem Health)

Mobile 072 123 2413

05 October 2020

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

SUPPORT FOR EFTEON PROPOSAL

I have been introduced to the EFTEON proposed project through a PhD student Mr. Desmond Musetsho. I have discussed it with various colleagues within our department and we see the EFTEON programme as an opportunity to expand our research into the areas concerned and therefore do support the initiative. This may involve M&D students and academic staff not only from the Department of Environmental Sciences but also other departments within the College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, e.g. Geography, Life and Consumer Sciences, Agriculture. The Department of Environmental Sciences (about 69 academics) have 4 programme groups:- Nature Conservation, Horticulture, Environmental Management and Environmental Sciences. If required a list of academic's fields of research can be made available.

I would like to make use of the opportunity in wishing UNIVEN all the best with their application.

Yours sincerely

Prof WAJ Nel

Department of Environmental Sciences

Date 05 October 2020

**FRIEDRICH-SCHILLER-
UNIVERSITÄT
JENA**

**Faculty of Chemistry and Earth Sciences
Department for Earth Observation**

Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena · Institute of Geography 07737 Jena

Prof. Stefan Foord
Department of Zoology
School of Mathematical and Natural Sciences
University of Venda
Private Bag X5050
Thohoyandou, 0950
South Africa

Prof. Dr. Christiane Schmallius
Full Professor

Löbdergraben 32
07743 Jena

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Telefax: 0 36 41 9-48882
E-Mail: c.schmallius@uni-jena.de

Jena, 27. September 2020

Letter of support for EFTEON landscape proposal (Soutpansberg Luvuvhu)

Dear Prof. Foord,

thank you very much for your invitation to help establishing the Soutpansberg Luvuvhu “research landscape” recognized by the funding EFTEON programme, the South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) and the National Research Foundation of South Africa. With this letter, the Department for Earth Observation, Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena (FSU), confirms to fully support the landscape proposal and the long-term research to be conducted in the Soutpansberg Luvuvhu landscape. More specifically, the FSU will contribute to this initiative with a range of remote sensing data and products over the Vuwani area. These include, but are not limited to, multispectral, thermal and radar-based satellite time series, a digital elevation model and historical aerial photographs. We trust that these and other information layers will provide the scientific basis for investigating the status and dynamics of different land surface parameters and will help gaining a better understanding of the Soutpansberg Luvuvhu landscape.

Yours sincerely,

Prof. Dr. Christiane Schmallius

Thünen Institute (AK) · Bundesallee 50 · 38116 Braunschweig/Germany

Professor **Stefan Foord**
Department of Zoology
Chemistry and Life Sciences Building
University of Venda
Private Bag X5050
0950
South Africa

**Institute of Climate-Smart
Agriculture**

Dr. Christian Brümmer
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christian.bruegger@thuenen.de
www.thuenen.de

your References

our References

Date

11.09.2020

Letter of Support for the EFTEON Landscape Proposal of Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu

Dear Professor Foord,

This letter is to express my full support to the joint proposal of the Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu landscape as response to the call for EFTEON landscape nominations of SAEON.

The proposed EFTEON landscape of Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu would support our intentions in building further research collaborations around the Vuwani Eddy Covariance flux tower, as well as other local infrastructures and sampling campaigns, to better understand the carbon dynamics in South African ecosystems. The unique feature of the Vuwani flux tower is that it offers a comparison between a peri-urban, heavily human-modified site, and the nearby Phalaborwa (Malopeni) tower at the Kruger National Park.

Our Micrometeorology group at the Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture has collaborated with the University of Venda Vuwani Science Resource Centre for many years, in the framework of the project *Adaptive Resilience in Southern African Ecosystems* (ARS AfricaE, 2014-2017) and its follow-up project *Ecosystem Management Support for Climate Change in Southern Africa* (EMSAfrica, 2018-2021). During these projects, our collaboration involved the construction, installation and maintenance of the Vuwani flux tower. We also organised a Winter School on greenhouse gas measurements, with focus on eddy covariance flux measurements, at the Vuwani site in 2019 in collaboration with SAEON/EFTEON, and trained Vuwani Centre staff members on tower maintenance via apprenticeships. Our current collaboration also involves the production of public materials on climate change and greenhouse gas measurements at the Vuwani Science Resource Centre.

The Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute, Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries – Thünen Institute in brief – consists of 14 specialized institutes that carry out research and provide policy advice in the fields of economy, ecology and technology.
President: Prof. Dr. Folkhard Isermeyer

Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture · Head: Prof. Dr. Heinz Flessa · Secretariat: +49 531 596-2602

We would be very pleased to see the Vuwani flux tower, in its full current instrumentation, to be utilized as part of the EFTEON landscapes initiative when the EMSAfrica project is over. We are in full agreement of openly sharing the data collected during the projects.

We propose to continue collaborations at the site and with the University of Venda, as well as other proposal partners, in various ways:

- Developing joint research proposals for bilateral and multilateral programmes covering relevant research topics;
- Establishing co-supervision of students and doctoral researchers, with exchange visits between our institutes to strengthen the students' technical or analytical skills;
- Establishing staff exchange visits between institutes, to enhance technical or analytical skills;
- Running further collaborative workshops and trainings around the topic of greenhouse gas observations, with special focus on eddy covariance flux measurements.

Yours sincerely,

Dr. Christian Brümmer, Head of Research Group Micrometeorology

GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT
GÖTTINGEN

Tropical Plant Production and Agricultural Systems Modelling (TROPAGS)
Grisebachstr. 6 · 37077 Göttingen

Professor Stefan Foord
Department of Zoology
Chemistry and Life Sciences Building
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Private Bag X5050
0950
South Africa

Prof. Dr. Reimund P. Rötter
(Scientific Coordinator)
South African Limpopo Landscape Network
(SALLnet)

Tropical Plant Production and Agricultural
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(Administrative Coordinator)
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24/09/2020

Letter of Support for the EFTEON Landscape Proposal of Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu

Dear Professor Foord,

I write to you to express my full support to the joint proposal of the Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu landscape as response to the call for EFTEON landscape nominations of SAEON.

The proposed EFTEON landscape of Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu supports our aim to sustain and further develop our research collaboration within the Northern Limpopo region with the common goal to examine the functioning and resilience of its multi-functional landscapes under the conditions of climate change /global change -- an objective shared with our project SALLnet (South African Limpopo Landscapes Network) under the SPACES II programme.

Our research group at Göttingen, coordinating since 2014 a research partnership of three German and three South African universities/research organizations has collaborated with the University of Venda successfully for many years. This long-term cooperation has generated a considerable number of joint activities, such as:

- scientific publications,
- workshops,
- fieldwork activities,
- capacity building and training measures,
- student exchanges, and
- the co-supervision of MSc and PhD students.

Members of SALLnet (a.o. Prof. Rötter, Prof. Isselstein, Prof. Feil, Prof. Linstädter, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Scheiter) have indicated their strong interest in supporting and participating in the Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu landscape project.

Thematically, the collaboration would focus notably on examining and analysing ecosystem services, and on assessing and modelling the impact of climate change and socio-economic developments on different land use types to develop sustainable land use options.

- Should the proposal be funded, SALLnet intends to cooperate in the resulting research efforts. This may include, but is not limited to, various joint activities (e.g. development of further joint research projects, workshops and conferences, institutional exchanges of research staff and students)

We are in full agreement of openly sharing the data collected during the project and look forward to the approval of the proposal and to a successful collaboration in the project.

Sincerely,

Reimund P. Rötter

(Chair of TROPAGS and Dean of Research, Agricultural Faculty, University of Göttingen)

Cc:

Prof. Dr. Anja Linstädter, Biodiversity Research and Systematic Botany, University of Potsdam, Germany

Dr. Simon Scheiter, Senckenberg Biodiversität und Klima Forschungszentrum (SBiK-F), Frankfurt/Main, Germany

23 September 2020

EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape

Letter of Support

I am writing in full support of the EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape proposal. I am principle investigator on Durham University's Primate & Predator Project, and we have been conducting long-term research within the Soutpansberg for nearly two decades, and established our own field station in 2012. Based at Lajuma Research Centre our research is structured around three key themes:

- 1) To assess the role of mountainous regions in biodiversity and large mammal conservation
- 2) To understand the behavioural ecology of predator-prey interactions focusing on diurnal primates and their predators as a model system
- 3) To evaluating the nature and extent of human-wildlife interaction within the Soutpansberg Mountains through interdisciplinary methods integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches

Our research is thus well aligned to the objectives of the EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape proposal and we would be delighted to combine our ongoing research activities with this exciting initiative.

Since 2012 we have run a large camera-trapping monitoring programme, with the initial survey area recently expanding to over 200km² through partnership with the Endangered Wildlife Trust and expansion to integrate their new Medike properties. This effort has highlighted a precipitous decline in the resident leopard population (e.g. Williams et al., 2017), as well as generating a wealth of data on the medium-large mammal community inhabiting the mountains. Through collaboration with Panthera and the Limpopo Leopard Project, we also run annual surveys allowing our data to feed into regional assessments for leopards (Pitman et al., 2017) and other large carnivores (e.g. brown hyaenas: Williams et al, in press). Each of these surveys constitute important baselines for assessing the impact of future conservation actions.

A key element of our ongoing research is to understand the human dimensions of human-wildlife interactions, and to develop approaches to mitigate the negative impacts on humans and wildlife from living in shared landscapes (e.g. Constant et al., 2015; Chase Grey et al., 2017). An important component of this has been to adopt a knowledge co-production approach, particularly in the evaluation of methods for mitigating the impacts of primate crop-foraging on farms (e.g. Findlay & Hill, in press; in review). Through funding from the Earthwatch Institute and international donors, and in collaboration with the African Institute for Conservation Ecology, we also run a community outreach and

education programme, providing support for improving livestock protection and animal husbandry, methods for reducing crop losses, as well as working with local schools to provide educational activities for the local children. We see enormous potential to integrate these activities with the proposed initiatives of the EFTEON Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape project.

Please do not hesitate to contact me if you require further information on the support we can offer the proposal. The application receives of very strongest endorsement and we advocate for the selection of the Soutpansberg as an EFTEON node.

Yours faithfully,

Professor Russell Hill
Joint Head of Department
Project Lead, Primate & Predator Project

References:

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- Pitman, R.T., Fattedbert, J., Williams, S.T., Williams, K.S., Hill, R.A., Hunter, L., Robinson, H., Power, J., Swanepoel, L., Slotow, R. & Balme, G.A. (2017) Cats, connectivity and conservation: incorporating datasets and integrating scales for wildlife management. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 54:1687-1689.
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- Williams, S.T., Williams, K.S., Lewis, B. & Hill, R.A. (2017) Population dynamics and threats to an apex predator outside protected areas: Implications for carnivore management. *Royal Society Open Science* 4: 161090.

4 September 2020

Letter of support from the Endangered Wildlife Trust for an EFTEON node in the Soutpansberg

Attention: EFTEON selection panel
c/o Dr Gregor Feig

The Endangered Wildlife Trust (EWT) is a non-governmental, non-profit, conservation organisation, founded in 1973 and operating throughout southern Africa. The EWT conserves threatened species and ecosystems in southern Africa by initiating research and conservation action programmes, implementing projects that mitigate threats facing species diversity and supporting sustainable natural resource management. The EWT furthermore communicates the principles of sustainable living through awareness programmes to the broadest possible constituency for the benefit of the region.

The EWT has a dedicated Conservation Science Unit which drives research and coordinates data collection and collation. The CSU helps to build the evidence-base for good conservation practice in the EWT and across the sector and works along the conservation evidence value chain, starting with good project design, data capture and documentation in the field, data curation and management, through to analyses, publication and dissemination of results. We build capacity and provide technical expertise in conservation-relevant science, which ultimately leads to robust conservation practice in the field. The EWT's Biodiversity Data Bank currently houses 194 of our own biodiversity datasets, 141 of which are still active. The Data Bank was set up to ensure that we don't lose any datasets on individual computers, and ensures the longevity of datasets and sharing of data for reuse in research and to inform conservation planning and sustainable development.

The EWT is an associate node of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and we are part of the African group of nodes, one of the most active regional groupings within GBIF. We continue to make our data freely available on the GBIF platform, including over 29,000 Cheetah and crane occurrence records, which have been downloaded over 3,500 times each, and reused and cited in several scientific papers.

The Conservation Science Unit houses a central repository for all of the EWT's research-related data, as well as all of our scientific publications, which we report on annually. We share data on request for research, conservation planning and environmental impact assessments, among others, as well as publishing our data online through GBIF or SABIF. We regularly publish results of our work in peer-reviewed journals and research reports, along with collaborators and students.

Physical Address: Plot 27 and 28 Austin Road, Glen Austin AH, Midrand, 1685
Gauteng, South Africa

Postal Address: Postnet Suite # 027, Postnet Suite 002, Private Bag X08, Wierda Park 0149
Gauteng, South Africa

Tel: +27(0)11 372 3600 **Fax:** +27(0)11 608 4682 **Email:** ewt@ewt.org.za **Web:** www.ewt.org.za

The Endangered Wildlife Trust is a non-profit, public benefit organisation dedicated to conserving species and ecosystems in southern Africa to the benefit of all people.

NPO Number: 015-502, **PBO number:** 930 001 777, **Member of IUCN** - The International Union for Conservation of Nature

**ENDANGERED
WILDLIFE TRUST**
Protecting forever, together.

In the Soutpansberg the EWT is in the process of coordinating and assisting with the proclamation of a large consolidated Nature Reserve (>27,000hectares) across the western Soutpansberg. The EWT has a vested interest and long-term commitment to this proposed protected area cemented by the fact that the EWT owns two of the properties within the Western Soutpansberg Nature reserve. Since initiating our formal involvement in the area in 2017 we have established and continue to drive a number of research efforts including but not limited to an extensive camera trap array across our properties and extending the array run by Durham University based at Lajuma Research Centre, a detailed research project focused on the globally Endangered *Warburgia salutaris* (Pepper-bark Tree), research linked to pangolin habitat suitability, citizen science diversity trails, alien invasive plant species mapping and monitoring (along with our clearing project) and water level-loggers have been installed, in collaboration with Duquesne University manage an electronic weather station based at Medike, to monitor catchment functioning and water retention. We also had two herpetological experts stationed on our Medike Nature Reserve property (on the Sand River) for almost a year, during which time they conducted extensive reptile, amphibian and other faunal surveys adding considerably to our understanding of the biodiversity of the property and surrounding areas. In addition, wildlife mortality data are collected on a 3.7 km transect of railway line which transects the EWTs Medike West property. Data are fed monthly into the EWT's Wildlife and Transport Programme database.

Given the EWTs long-term interest and involvement in the research and conservation of the Soutpansberg we would value the consolidated data collection effort leveraged by an EFTEON node in the area. We would be able to both contribute to this and to utilize the data generated in order to inform conservation action across the region, understand ecosystem service provision potential and degradation and of course assist/mitigate down-stream user impacts linked to this.

We strongly support the selection of the Soutpansberg as an EFTEON node and look forward to helping build a robust research centre representative of the northern part of South Africa.

Yours Sincerely,

Dr Ian Little
Senior Manager: Habitats
Endangered Wildlife Trust

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The Endangered Wildlife Trust is a non-profit, public benefit organisation dedicated to conserving species and ecosystems in southern Africa to the benefit of all people.

NPO Number: 015-502, **PBO number:** 930 001 777, **Member of IUCN** - The International Union for Conservation of Nature

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3 October 2020

To whom it may concern

Support for EFTEON “Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape” proposal

ZZ2 is an agricultural company that has been operating in northern Limpopo Province for generations. We produce primary agricultural products, most notably tomatoes, avocados and blueberries in the region. Our practices aim to be ecologically sensitive and environmentally sustainable. In order to achieve these goals, we place a big focus on research and environmental monitoring.

The northern parts of Limpopo Province has great potential from an agricultural point of view. The climate and soils are favorable for a range of sub-tropical and arid area crops. Big potential for high value “super foods” (e.g. blueberries) also exist. The agricultural potential also presents a very promising avenue for socio-economic development in a sustainable and diverse value chain.

Data and insights emanating from the EFTEON project may be very valuable in optimizing and improving productivity on existing agricultural developments (both large scale operations and medium to small scale farmers can find value). The EFTEON data will create more insight into where the best places are to focus future agricultural developments to ensure the dual goals of sustainable economic growth and environmental protection / ecological functioning of catchment systems.

Some of the research and monitoring work that the ZZ2's Research and Development department had been pursuing locally include, water quality monitoring, aquifer mapping and monitoring, climate monitoring, biodiversity monitoring and ecological rehabilitation of IAP sites. Further, we maintain positive relationships with various research institutions and universities locally and internationally.

We fully support the EFTEON proposal and will be willing to assist where we can, to ensure the project reaches its goals.

Wiam Haddad
ZZ2 R&D

DIRECTORS / DIREKTEURE:

PROF. AJ ANTONITES, HJ DU PLESSIS, GAC EHLERS, JH GROBLER, PROF. D HOLM,
PROF. E HOLM, JT KOORTS (CHAIRMAN / VOORSITTER), AE RECH, JS STANBURY,
BJ VAN ZYL, CB VAN ZYL, PHILÉ VAN ZYL, PJ VAN ZYL, TD VAN ZYL

AICE

African Institute for Conservation Ecology

African Institute for Conservation Ecology

NPC registration number: 2016/000009/08

Non-Profit organisation: 187-801 NPO

Public Benefit Organisation: 930060171

Tel: 082 817 4679

28 October 2019

Letter of support from the African Institute for Conservation Ecology (AICE) for an EFTEON node in the Soutpansberg – hosted by University of Venda

Attention: EFTEON selection panel
c/o Dr Gregor Feig

The African Institute for Conservation Ecology (AICE) is a non-governmental, non-profit, conservation organisation, founded in 2016 operating throughout South Africa, with a specific focus in the Vhembe Biosphere reserve. The AICE's main focus is conservation of predators and predation ecosystem services through long term ecological research and conservation initiatives. Specifically the AICE focus its actions towards the support of conservation and academic institutions to assist upcoming students with logistical support to sustain long term ecological studies. At the AICE we believe that sustainable conservation actions can only be achieved through bottom-up processes, with strong focus on student and community education.

The AICE have a strong focus and presence in the current proposed EFTEON node in the Soutpansberg. These include conservation and research actions focussed towards sustainable livestock-carnivore mitigation options at the Buysdorp communities in west Soutpansberg; sustainable pest rodent management through the application of ecologically based rodent management programs that incorporate natural predation as biological control (east Soutpansberg); long term camera trapping at key sites (Venetia, Blouberg, Langjan and Marimane Nature Reserves) for the Functional Biodiversity Project (NRF funded); Mopane worm as keystone species at Venetia Nature reserve and Masisi communities (Pafuri area of Kruger National park); carnivore cultural knowledge generated through community led and facilitated discussion among the north-western boundary of Kruger National Park (Punda Maria to Pafuri; including Makuya and Makuleki communities).

Current and future projects that would be strategic in the EFTEON Soutpansberg node include Lion (*Panthera leo*) recovery in the northern section of KNP (through collaboration with EWT Carnivore conservation project). This project will be based at Nthakeni river camp on the Mutali river (used as an AICE research base) with a focus on community led lion conservation through community facilitated research (community poaching monitoring, community camera trap monitoring). The Nthakeni research camp is also a strategic monitoring site for the Mutale River entering the KNP and feeding the Levubu River.

Due to the strong focus on the AICE on student logistical support we believe these projects will be a valuable contribution to the goals of an EFTEON node in the Soutpansberg. Since University of Venda is the most northerly university in South Africa, which also fall in the Vhembe Biosphere, and its

students mainly originate from the Venda rural landscapes, we believe such an EFTEON node will be a major impetus for locally driven conservation and monitoring actions. Furthermore, the combination of protected and transformed landscapes monitored by the AICE provides the ideal areas to monitor the impact of the current global change drivers (e.g. human density, land transformation, water extraction etc.).

As such from the AICE we strongly support the Soutpansberg and University of Venda as an EFTEON node. We strongly believe the current social and intellectual capital at the University of Venda will lead to robust long term data collection and research.

Yours Sincerely

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Lourens Swanepoel', is written over a faint, light-colored rectangular stamp or watermark.

Dr Lourens Swanepoel

Director AICE

www.aice.org

Lajuma Familie Trust (IT 7219/96). Operating as Lajuma Research Centre
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P.O. Box 522 Louis Tichardt 0920, South Africa
E-mail: bibi@lajuma.com

16th September 2020

Letter of support for selection of the Soutpansberg-Luvuvhu Landscape as an EFTEON site

Attention: Dr Gregor Feig

The Lajuma Familie Trust has been operating Lajuma Research Centre within Luvhondo Nature Reserve, western Soutpansberg since 2000 where it is also a landowner. With links to international and South African universities, in particular the University of Venda, and conservation organisations Lajuma has two main operations: hosting long-term university researchers in a wilderness venue and hosting university and conservation groups for shorter-term research and training programmes. Lajuma facilitated and hosted research and sampling has led to substantial and annually increasing ecological knowledge of the Soutpansberg and academic output including 21 PhD degrees, over 60 MSc and Honours degrees and 88 peer-reviewed publications, adding to the scientific knowledge base and skills development. From 2017 through 2019 Lajuma annually reached ~280 participants from 18 countries and 21 academic institutions.

Lajuma staff were instrumental in the proclamation of the Luvhondo Nature Reserve, the largest Protected Area in the western Soutpansberg and on the regional scale the proclamation of the UNESCO Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, underpinning these with a scientific basis. Working with local scientists and conservationists, research facilitated by Lajuma has highlighted the importance of the conservation of the western Soutpansberg unlike any other initiative. Lajuma has utilised this research by inputting into local and regional conservation planning and projects, as well as training underprivileged South African students for whom funds are raised. Early research on leopard populations and inventorying fauna and flora has scaled to long-term monitoring including annual altitudinal transects by the University of Venda, annual leopard population censuses by Panthera and the development of the Durham University Primate and Predator research and outreach programme based at Lajuma.

Lajuma has an enduring commitment to research and conservation within the region and fully endorses the application to EFTEON. Lajuma projects would be able to both utilise EFTEON data as well as provide support and sampling opportunities to this programme.

Yours sincerely,

Dr Bibi Linden
Manager Academic programme

On behalf of the trustees of the Lajuma Familie Trust.